

PROJECT REPORT

**Wireless Body Area Network
(Development of Physiological Sensor Suite)**

Submitted by

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In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award

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Institute of Nuclear Medicine and Allied Sciences (INMAS)

Defense Research and Development Organization (DRDO)

Ministry of Defense

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **Amit Kumar Jaiswal**, a student of **M.Sc. (Electronics)** of Deen Dayal Upadhyay Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur (U.P.) has completed his project entitled '**Wireless Body Area Network: Development of Physiological Sensor Suite**' from August 11, 2011 to February 15, 2012 under my supervision and guidance.

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DECLARATION

I, **Amit Kumar Jaiswal** hereby declare that the dissertation report, entitled '**Wireless Body Area Network: Development of Physiological Sensor Suite**' submitted to **DDU Gorakhpur Univesity, Gorakhpur** in the partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the **M.Sc. degree in Electronics** is a record of disseration work done by me during **August 10, 2011 to February 15, 2012** under the supervision and guidance of **Sh. Sushil Chandra (F)** Head, Bio-Medical Engineering Department at **INMAS, DRDO, Delhi**.

The matter presented in this thesis has not been submitted in any other University/ Institute for the award of any degree.

Date: 15/02/2012

Place: INMAS, Delhi

Signature of Candidate

(Amit Kumar Jaiswal)

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Amit Kumar Jaiswal

ABOUT ORGANISATION

Genesis & Growth

DRDO was formed in 1958 from the amalgamation of the then already functioning Technical Development Establishment (TDEs) of the Indian Army and the Directorate of Technical Development & Production (DTDP) with the Defence Science Organisation (DSO). DRDO was then a small organisation with 10 establishments or laboratories. Over the years, it has grown multi-directionally in terms of the variety of subject disciplines, number of laboratories, achievements and stature.

Today, DRDO is a network of more than 50 laboratories which are deeply engaged in developing defence technologies covering various disciplines, like aeronautics, armaments, electronics, combat vehicles, engineering systems, instrumentation, missiles, advanced computing and simulation, special materials, naval systems, life sciences, training, information systems and agriculture. Presently, the Organisation is backed by over 5000 scientists and about 25,000 other scientific, technical and supporting personnel. Several major projects for the development of missiles, armaments, light combat aircrafts, radars, electronic warfare systems etc are on hand and significant achievements have already been made in several such technologies.

Vision

Make India prosperous by establishing world class science and technology base and provide our Defence Services decisive edge by equipping them with internationally competitive systems and solution.

Mission

- Design, develop and lead to production state-of-the-art sensors, weapon systems, platforms and allied equipment for our Defence Services.
- Provide technological solutions to the Services to optimise combat effectiveness and to promote well-being of the troops.
- Develop infrastructure and committed quality manpower and build strong indigenous technology base.

INMAS (DRDO)

Historical Background

At the instance of Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru, the first Prime Minister of India, a RaDIATion Cell was established in 1956 at Defence Science Laboratory, Delhi. The initial assignment was to undertake a study on the consequences of the use of nuclear and other weapons of mass destruction. But it was soon realised that nuclear energy can also be harnessed for the good of the mankind.

Radioisotopes could find peaceful medical applications. The scope of work was, therefore, enlarged and the cell upgraded to RaDIATion Medicine Division in 1959. As awareness increased, so did the work and a full-fledged establishment was created in 1961 and named Institute of Nuclear Medicine and Allied Sciences. Since then we have traversed a long way, carrying out R&D and providing service as a model of excellence in various aspects of Nuclear Medicine and Allied Sciences. The activities of the Institute have proliferated enormously over the years. Its areas of activity have been diversified to cover many fields of raDIATion and Bio-medical sciences. Availability of large number of diagnostic facilities (MRI, PET-CT, Gamma Camera, non-invasive imaging, Hormone assay techniques etc.) and basic research facilities (Flow Cytometers, Confocal microscope, Gamma irraDIATors, RT-PCR, HPLC, Fluorimeter etc) under one roof is uniqueness of this institute.

INMAS is engaged in research in the field of basic and applied medical sciences including development of Radioprotectors and treatment modalities for management of raDIATion emergencies, endocrinology, Biodosimetry, development of potential pharmaceuticals as contrast agents for nuclear medicine and magnetic resonance imaging and strategies for Chemical -Biological-Radiological and Nuclear (CBRN) defencè, besides futuristic research on neuro-cognitive disorders.

Vision

The Vision of INMAS has been identified as to be a centre of excellence in biomedical and clinical research with special reference to ionizing radiation.

Mission

The Mission of INMAS is clinical research in nuclear medicine and non-invasive imaging methods with a focus on biological radio protectors and thyroid disorders.

Core Competence

Area I: Biological Radioprotection

- Modification of RaDIATion Response
- Development of Radioprotectors
- Biological Dosimeters

Area II: Management of Thyroid Disorders

- Role of Genetic Factors & Autoimmunity in Thyroid Disorders
- Non-invasive Diagnosis of Thyroid Disorders using RIA & Related Techniques
- Management of Thyroid Disorders
- Radioiodine Therapy

Area III: Nuclear and Medical Imaging

- Non-invasive Diagnosis of Anatomical Lesions with Special Reference to CNS and CVS
- Development of Radiopharmaceuticals & Magneto-pharmaceuticals for Infection, Metabolic and Functional Imaging

Facility available

- PET Cyclotron Beam Facility
- Nude Mice Facility
- Flow cytometer
- Advanced Digital Radiology Bone Densitometer
- NMR Spectrometer

BASIC RESEARCH FACILITIES

- Gamma Irradiation or 220
- Flowcytometer Facscalibur
- ELISA Reader (96-Well Plate)
- Cobalt Teletherapy Unit
- Gamma and Beta Counter
- Confocal Microscope
- Fluorescence Microscope and Comet Analysis System
- DIC Microscope
- High performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)
- Technical Library
- Experimental Animal Facility

MEDICAL FACILITIES

- Dual Head SPECT
- MRI
- PET-CT Scanner
- Ultrasound
- Mammography
- Biochemistry Analyser
- Physiotherapy Machine
- Pulmonary Function Test
- X-Ray Machine
- Holter Monitoring
- TMT
- Echocardiography

- Elec SYS 1010
- Dental Chair
- SR 300 for Radio-Immuno-Assay

Programs Conducted

- **DRM (Diploma in Radiation Medicine), Delhi University**

This is a two years formal teaching course at INMAS continuing at Nuclear Medicine Department.

- **DNB (Diplomats of National Board)**

INMAS has got accreditation by National Board of Examination for a 3 year DNB programme consisting of 2 primary and 2 secondary students. The course has already commenced from 2006.

INMAS has joined the prestigious group of medical colleges imparting DNB courses (post graduation in the field of radio-diagnosis). Four primary and two secondary candidates are undergoing this programme.

- **Academic Participation**

INMAS scientists participate in teaching as faculty members in various prestigious academic institutes.

- **Ph.D Programme**

More than 40 Ph.D. students are pursuing their research work in various fields of RaDIATion Sciences & are enrolled with prestigious academic institutions.

- **Summer/ Project Training**

INMAS is imparting training to B.Sc/ M.Sc/ B.Tech/ M.Tech students coming from various academic institutions for summer /Project training.

Wireless Body Area Network: Development of Physiological Sensor Suite

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to develop a light wearable physiological sensor suite integrated with many electronic bio-sensors on a single acquisition board to take most of bio-signal and then transmit these signal data wirelessly to the base station located at many kilometers far from them for the study and monitoring of physiological status of army 'jawans' on real time.

In this task the light weight, small size, low cost, low power, open sources and multi channel acquisition board Arduino Mega 2560 rev3 is used as the node platform. All the sensors are as possible as of light weight and handmade to reduce the cost and system weight.

Here temperature, Heart rate/pulse rate, Galvanic Skin Response and Electromyogram sensing is done up to real hardware implementation and ECG & EEG sensing is done only up to virtual hardware due to much noisy response and the concept for these sensing is studied completely.

The wireless transmission of bio-signals (Temperature, HR, GSR, EMG) to PC is done for short range of 2 meters via Bluetooth. The wireless sensor networking part is done conceptually but unable to implement on real hardware due to single node availability.

These results signify that it is possible to implement all the sensors in a single suite but noise is the main problem for acquiring the actual response mainly in ECG and EEG. So now we are able to develop it further for EEG and ECG also with better noise removal logic and with long range.

MASTER THESIS

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1.1- General

Physiological Sensor suit is based on Wireless Body area Networking in which the bio-signals are taken out by different sensors and electrodes. Then it's amplified, filtered and converted into electrical form by an integrated circuit board and then after it is transmitted to the base station wirelessly for cognitive analysis, medical use, and other purposes.

1.2- Objective

To design a physiological sensor suite for the acquisition of bio-signals of human body and transmit them wirelessly to the base station (Computer) for medical, cognitive and other monitoring.

1.3- Basic principles

Actually muscles of our body generate electric current due to voltage difference among different organs. This voltage is generated by neurons burning and other electrical activities in cells. It is different in magnitude for different organs. For some organs it is in microvolt range and for some it is in millivolt. They generate an electrical signal, called bio-signals. Besides these electrical bio-signals there are some non-electrical signal also. These electrical signal (small electric current) may be taken out by some conductive electrodes for analysis. If we have a multi-channel processor , we can integrate many of the sensors and/or electrodes on a single board implanted in a wearable suite for real time analysis.

1.4- Bio -signal-Machine interface

Machines are controlled by using bio-signals. Use of electrical bio-signals measured on scalp and corresponding to mental relaxation and concentration tasks in order to control an object in a video game. Also many small or large machine may be controlled by some bio-signals. The main target is to controlled in systematic manner as we wish.

The mechanical bio-signal and machine interfacing was done many century ago. The acoustic signal interfacing is also done up to some limits. But now our focus is to interface thermal, electrical, optical and other signals with machines.

1.5- Instruments

Bio-signals are intrinsically very-very small in magnitude and has no significant usable value. So, for its significant use we have to magnify it with decreasing the noise. Since these signals are of very-very less magnitude and there are so many sources of noise therefore the noise reduction is our top priority. It may be possible by digital and analog (mixed) signal processing.

For amplification we can't use simple op-amp because of low amplitude of intrinsic signal. Therefore we use here instrumentation amplifier.

Since the whole system is wearable so the weighing factor is more significant. So the weight of sensors, electrodes and acquisition board must be of as low weight as possible.

Scope of project

When we want to diagnosis, monitor or enhance any one's physiological status, the first task is to bring him at the station where these facilities are available. Then we have to create an artificial environment. If we implant the wearable facilities on the subject then we can monitor him in real time and also in real environment. This is very-very helpful for monitoring the health and position of army 'Jawans' by their commander or base station. Other than this it would be also very useful for disabled persons in medical field for their real time diagnosis and treatment and also in the field of telemedicine.

1.6 Report Outline

The entire work is supported by Biomedical Engineering Department, INMAS, DRDO (Ministry of Defense, India). It's a part of major project VE-CARE (Virtual Environment Cognitive Assessment Rehabilitation and Enhancement).

The report details are as follows

Chapter-1 introduces about the project basic theme and its specification and general criteria.

Chapter-2 deals with the basic domain for the study the electronic concepts of bio-signals and points of organs to acquiring them electronically, variation of signal by different events and need of wireless physiological sensor suite.

Chapter-3 deals with the hardware and software for sensors implementation, programming for data acquisition and to show it graphically.

Chapter-4 explains briefly methodology for sensor implementation and process of acquiring and transmitting the bio-signals wirelessly to the laptop.

Chapter-5 explain than can be machines are controlled by bio-signals.

Chapter-6 explains the conceptual study of Wireless Sensor Networking over Wireless Body Area Networking.

Chapter-7 deals with the Result and Discussion i.e. performance of the circuits program developed for completing the project.

Bio-signal is a summarizing term for all kinds of signals that can be (continually) measured and monitored from biological beings. The term bio-signal is often used to mean bio-electrical signal but in fact, bio-signal refers to both electrical and non-electrical signals.

Mainly there are four types of bio-signals, they are:

Electrical bio-signals ("bio-electrical" signals) are usually taken to be (changes in) electric currents produced by the sum of electrical potential differences across a specialized tissue, organ or cell system like the nervous system. Other than this the optical bio-signal is also significant.

Thus, among the best-known bio-electrical signals are the

- Electroencephalogram (EEG)
- Electromyogram (EMG)
- Electrocardiogram (ECG)
- Electroculogram (EOG)
- Galvanic skin response (GSR)
- Heart Rate Variability (HRV)

Electrical currents and changes in electrical resistances across tissues can also be measured from plants.

Bio-signals may also refer to any non-electrical signal that is capable of being monitored from biological beings, such as temperature, mechanical signals (e.g. the mechanomyogram or MMG), acoustic signals (e.g. phonetic and non-phonetic utterances, breathing), chemical signals (e.g. pH, oxygenation) and optical signals (e.g. movements).

Actually muscles of our body generate electric current due to voltage difference among different organs which are really the electrical bio-signal.

2.1-Brain signals & EEG (Electroencephalogram)

Brain is an electric generator The number of nerve cells in the brain has been estimated to be on the order of 10^{11} . The amplitude of the nerve impulse is about 100 mV; it lasts about 1 ms.

The bioelectric impressed current density $\bar{J}^i$ associated with neuronal activation produces an electric field, which can be measured on the surface of the head or directly on the brain tissue. The electric field was described by Equation 7.10 for a finite inhomogeneous model. This equation is repeated here:

$$4\pi\sigma\Phi(r) = \int_v \bar{J}^i \cdot \nabla\left(\frac{1}{r}\right) dv + \sum_j \int_{s_j} (\sigma_j'' - \sigma_j') \Phi \nabla\left(\frac{1}{r}\right) \cdot d\bar{S}_j$$

Fig: Brain's inner part

Fig: Brain's neurons

Fig: Frequency spectrum of normal EEG

2.1.1-Human Brain neurons also known as a neurone or nerve cell is an electrically excitable cell that processes and transmits information by electrical and chemical signaling. Chemical signaling occurs via synapses, specialized connections with other cells. Neurons connect to each other to form neural networks. Neurons are the core components of the nervous system, which includes the brain, spinal cord, and peripheral ganglia. A number of specialized types of neurons exist: sensory neurons respond to touch, sound, light and numerous other stimuli affecting cells of the sensory organs that then send signals to the spinal cord and brain. Motor neurons receive signals from the brain and spinal cord, cause muscle contractions, and affect glands. Inter-neurons connect neurons to other neurons within the same region of the brain or spinal cord.

The brain's electrical charge is maintained by billions of neurons. Neurons are electrically charged (or "polarized") by membrane transport proteins that pump ions across their membranes. Neurons are constantly exchanging ions with the extracellular milieu, for example to maintain resting potential and to propagate action potentials. Ions of like charge repel each other, and when many ions are pushed out of many neurons at the same time, they can push their neighbors, who push their neighbours, and so on, in a wave. This process is known as volume conduction. When the wave of ions reaches the electrodes on the scalp, they can push or pull electrons on the metal on the electrodes. Since

metal conducts the push and pull of electrons easily, the difference in push or voltage between any two electrodes can be measured by a voltmeter. Recording these voltages over time gives us the EEG.

The electric potentials generated by single neurons are far too small to be picked by EEG or MEG. EEG activity therefore always reflects the summation of the synchronous activity of thousands or millions of neurons that have similar spatial orientation. If the cells do not have similar spatial orientation, their ions do not line up and create waves to be detected. Pyramidal neurons of the cortex are thought to produce the most EEG signal because they are well-aligned and fire together. Because voltage fields fall off with the square of distance, activity from deep sources is more difficult to detect than currents near the skull.

Scalp EEG activity shows oscillations at a variety of frequencies. Several of these oscillations have characteristic frequency ranges, spatial distributions and are associated with different states of brain functioning (e.g., waking and the various sleep stages). These oscillations represent synchronized activity over a network of neurons. The neuronal networks underlying some of these oscillations are understood (e.g., the thalamocortical resonance underlying sleep spindles), while many others are not (e.g., the system that generates the posterior basic rhythm). Research that measures both EEG and neuron spiking finds the relationship between the two is complex with the power of surface EEG in only two bands (gamma and delta) relating to neuron spike activity.

2.1.2-Electroencephalography

EEG is the recording of electrical activity along the scalp. EEG measures voltage fluctuations resulting from ionic current flows within the neurons of the brain. In clinical contexts, EEG refers to the recording of the brain's spontaneous electrical activity over a short period of time, usually 20–40 minutes, as recorded from multiple electrodes placed on the scalp. Diagnostic applications generally focus on the spectral content of EEG, that is, the type of neural oscillations that can be observed in EEG signals. In neurology, the main diagnostic application of EEG is in the case of epilepsy, other clinical use of EEG is in the diagnosis of coma, encephalopathy, and brain death.

Derivatives of the EEG technique include evoked potentials (EP), which involves averaging the EEG activity time-locked to the presentation of a stimulus of some sort (visual, somatosensory, or auditory). Event-related potentials (ERPs) refer to averaged EEG responses that are time-locked to more

complex processing of stimuli; this technique is used in cognitive science, cognitive psychology, and psychophysiological research.

2.1.3- Research use.

EEG is used extensively in neuroscience, cognitive science, cognitive psychology, and psychophysiological research.

Most of the cerebral signal observed in the scalp EEG falls in the range of 1–20 Hz (activity below or above this range is likely to be artifactual, under standard clinical recording techniques). These are classified as:

Fig: multi-channel EEG spectrum

2.1.4- Delta wave:: A delta wave is a high amplitude brain wave with a frequency of oscillation between 0–4 Hz.

Delta waves, like other brain waves, are recorded with an electro-encephalogram (EEG) and are usually associated with the deepest stages of sleep (3 and 4 NREM), also known as slow-wave sleep (SWS), and aid in characterizing the depth of sleep.

Delta waves, an EEG (electroencephalograph) one second

2.1.5- Theta wave:: A theta wave is an oscillatory pattern in EEG signals recorded either from inside the brain or from electrodes glued to the scalp with a frequency range of 6–10 Hz. Two types of theta rhythm have been described. The "*hippocampal theta rhythm*" is a strong oscillation that can be observed in the hippocampus and other brain structures in numerous species of mammals including rodents, rabbits, dogs, cats, bats, and marsupials. "*Cortical theta rhythms*" are low-frequency components of scalp EEG, usually recorded from humans.

2.1.6- Alpha wave:: Alpha waves are neural oscillations in the frequency range of 8–12 Hz arising from *synchronous* and *coherent (in phase/constructive)* electrical activity of thalamic pacemaker cells in humans. They are also called Berger's wave in memory of the founder of EEG.

2.1.7- Beta wave:: Beta wave, or beta rhythm, is the term used to designate the frequency range of human brain activity between 12 and 30 Hz (12 to 30 transitions or cycles per second). Beta waves are split into three sections: Low Beta Waves (12.5-16 Hz, "Beta 1 power"); Beta Waves (16.5–20 Hz, "Beta 2 power"); and High Beta Waves (20.5-28 Hz, "Beta 3 power").^[1] Beta states are the states associated with normal waking consciousness.

2.1.8- Gamma wave:: A gamma wave is a pattern of neural oscillation in humans with a frequency between 25 to 100 Hz, though 40 Hz is prototypical.

According to a popular theory, gamma waves may be implicated in creating the unity of conscious perception (the binding problem). However, there is no agreement on the theory; as a researcher suggests:

Whether or not gamma wave activity is related to subjective awareness is a very difficult question which cannot be answered with certainty at the present time.

2.1.9- Mu wave:: Mu waves, also known as the comb or wicket rhythm, are electromagnetic oscillations in the frequency range of 8–13 Hz and appear in bursts of at 9 – 11 Hz. Mu-wave patterns arise from synchronous and coherent (in phase/constructive) electrical activity of large groups of neurons in the human brain. This wave activity appears to be associated with the motor cortex (central scalp), and is diminished with movement or an intent to move, or when others are observed performing actions.. Recently, based on the conflicting evidence presented by mu-wave suppression experiments, Patricia Churchland has cautioned that "studies indicate that mu-suppression turns out to be the same in both high-functioning ASD subjects and healthy controls, hence disconfirming the hypothesis that mu-suppression is an index of mirror neuron activity. Alternately, if it is such an index, then disconfirming the hypothesis that mirror neuron activity is abnormal in ASD subjects." Mu waves are commonly detected by (EEG) or (MEG). The mu wave is an alpha wave like variant.

2.1.10- Electrode, Cable, Gel & Electrode placement

Electrode placement

EEG cap

EEG cable

EEG electrode

EEG Gel

Electrode is an electrical conductor used to make contact with brain scalp (a nonmetallic part). In EEG system it's actually a fine conductive and adhesive plate for well metal contacting with brain to data acq. board via EEG cable.

EEG cable is an electrical conductive multi-core wire to connect electrode and data acq. board capable to hook and hold the electrode and plug of data acq. board tightly. To avoid electrical noise it must be finely separated and covered by insulating materials.

EEG Gel is a paste to apply between the scalp and electrode to increase the connectivity and reduce the input impedance.

EEG Cap is a cap including many electrodes affixed in a defined manner to make easy the electrode placement and to reduce noise.

Electrode Placement: The 10-20 system or *International 10-20 system* is an internationally recognized method to describe and apply the location of scalp electrodes in the context of an EEG test or experiment. This system is based on the relationship between the location of an electrode and the underlying area of cerebral cortex. The "10" and "20" refer to the fact that the actual distances between adjacent electrodes are either 10% or 20% of the total front-back or right-left distance of the skull.

International 10-20 system of electrode placement in EEG

wave concentration in different parts

Each site has a letter to identify the lobe and a number to identify the hemisphere location. The letters F, T, C, P and O stand for frontal, temporal, central, parietal, and occipital lobes, respectively. Note that there exists no central lobe, the "C" letter is only used for identification purposes only. A "z" (zero) refers to an electrode placed on the midline. Even numbers (2,4,6,8) refer to electrode positions on the right hemisphere, whereas odd numbers (1,3,5,7) refer to those on the left hemisphere.

2.2- Heart electrical activity & Electrocardiography

1. Sinoatrial node
2. Atrioventricular node
3. Bundle of His
4. Left bundle branch
5. left anterior fascicle
6. left posterior fascicle
7. Left ventricle
8. Ventricular septum
9. Right ventricle
10. Right bundle branch

Heart; conduction system

Isolated conduction system of the heart

2.2.1- Electrical conduction system of the heart: The normal intrinsic electrical conduction of the heart allows electrical propagation to be transmitted from the Sinoatrial Node through both atria and forward to the Atrioventricular Node. Normal/baseline physiology allows further propagation from the AV node to the ventricle or Purkinje Fibers and respective bundle branches and subdivisions/fascicles. Both the SA and AV nodes stimulate the Myocardium. Time ordered stimulation of the myocardium allows efficient contraction of all four chambers of the heart, thereby allowing selective blood perfusion through both the lungs and systemic circulation.

2.2.2- Electrochemical mechanism: Cardiac neurons innervating the myocardium bear limited similarities to those of skeletal muscle as well as other important differences. Cardiac neurons are uniquely subject to influence by the sympathetic and parasympathetic influence of the autonomic nervous system unlike skeletal muscle.

2.2.3- Heart Electrical Activity: Like the spark-plug of an automobile it generates a number of "sparks" per minute. Each "spark" travels across a specialized electrical pathway and stimulates the muscle wall of the four chambers of the heart to contract (and thus empty) in a certain sequence or pattern. The upper chambers or atria are first stimulated. This is followed by a slight delay to allow the two atria (atria is plural for atrium and pronounced ay-tree-ya) to empty. Finally, the two ventricles are electrically stimulated.

In an automobile, the number of sparks per minute generated by a spark plug is increased when you press the gas pedal or accelerator. This revs up the motor. In case of the heart, adrenaline acts as a gas pedal and causes the sinus node to increase the number of sparks per minute, which in turn increases the heart rate. The release of adrenaline is controlled by the nervous system. The heart normally beats at around 72 times per minute and the sinus node speeds up during exertion, emotional stress, fever, etc., or whenever our body needs an extra boost of blood supply. In contrast, it slows down during rest or under the influence of certain medications. Well trained athletes also tend to have a slower heart beat.

Generation of PQRS waveform

PQRS system & Heart pumping system

2.2.4- Duration and characteristics of each major event in the cardiac cycle.

Event	Characteristics	Duration at 75 bpm (0.8 second cycle)
Atrial diastole Ventricular diastole	AV valves opened. Semilunar valves close. Ventricular filling.	0.4 seconds
Atrial systole Ventricular diastole	AV valves open. Semilunar valves closed. Ventricular filling.	0.1 seconds
Atrial diastole Ventricular systole	AV valves closed. Semilunar valves open. Blood pumped into aorta and pulmonary artery.	0.3 seconds

2.2.5- So, **ECG or EKG** is a transthoracic (across the thorax or chest) interpretation of the electrical activity of the heart over a period of Time, as detected by electrodes attached to the outer surface of the skin and recorded by a device external to the body. The recording produced by this noninvasive procedure is termed as electrocardiogram (also ECG or EKG). An electrocardiogram (ECG) is a test that records the electrical activity of the heart.

ECG is used to measure the rate and regularity of heartbeats as well as the size and position of the chambers, the presence of any damage to the heart, and the effects of drugs or devices used to regulate the heart (such as a pacemaker).

Most EKGs are performed for diagnostic or research purposes on human hearts, but may also be performed on animals, usually for research.

2.2.6- ECG measurement system: The ECG system is shown on Figure. The ECG system comprises four stages, each stage is as following:

Function blocks of the ECG system

Signal acquisition points in 3-lead

Figure 17-42 Electrocardiographic views of the heart
Copyright © 2009 Lippincott Williams & Wilkins. Individual's Resource 50:1056 to Anesthetics Critical Care Nursing, 4th Edition, Approach, eighth edition.

Signal acquisition points in 12-lead

Signal acquisition points in 12-lead

- (1) The first stage is a transducer—AgCl electrode, which convert ECG into electrical voltage. The voltage is in the range of 1 mV ~ 5 mV.
- (2) The second stage is an instrumentation amplifier which has a very high CMRR (90dB) and high gain (1000), with low power supply (+9V and -9V).
- (3) We use an opto-coupler (NEC PS2506) to isolate the In-Amp and output.
- (4) After the opto-coupler is a bandpass filter of 0.04 Hz to 150 Hz filter. It's implemented by cascading a low-pass filter and a high pass filter.

The ECG is converted into electrical voltage by electrodes. A typical surface electrode used for ECG recording is made of Ag/AgCl, as shown on Figure 3. The disposable electrodes are attached to the patients' skin and can be easily removed.

A disposable surface electrode.

The ECG cardiac cycle.

The cardiac mechanism of ECG is shown on Figure 4. In the top figure, the electrocardiogram (ECG) initiates the cardiac cycle. The cardiac sounds are also shown. The bottom figure shows that ejection occurs when the pressure in the left ventricle exceeds that in the arteries.

Once the electrodes convert the ECG into electrical voltage, these voltage can be fed into an instrumentation amplifier, and then be processed.

We measure the ECG by connecting two electrodes on the right and left chest respectively, as shown on Figure

(5) The body should be connected to ground of the circuits, so that we connect the leg to the ground. If the body is not grounded, no signal would be obtained.

Simplified ECG recording system

The ECG signals. The three signals are respectively probed from (1) In-Amp (2) Opto-Coupler (3) Filter.

2.2.7- Measured ECG signals: The three measured ECG signals, are respectively from the Instrumentation Amp, opto-coupler, and filter. The circuits function very well so that the three signals are almost identical to each other.

Measuring different region of the heart will obtain different ECG signals. The ECG signal shown on Figure 9 is one of the standard ECG signals.

2.2.8- 3-lead ECG: Three electrodes are needed for the 3-lead ECG. The chest leads represent 2 electrodes, while the third electrodes is placed on left leg.

2.3-Muscles electrical activity & Electromyography (EMG)

Electromyography (EMG) is a technique for evaluating and recording the electrical activity produced by skeletal muscles. EMG is performed using an instrument called an electro-myograph, to produce a record called an electromyogram. An electromyograph detects the electrical potential generated by muscle cells when these cells are electrically or neurologically activated. The signals can be analyzed to detect medical abnormalities, activation level, recruitment order or to analyze the biomechanics of human or animal movement.

Electrode placement in Surface EMG

needle placement in intermuscularEMG

2.3.1-Electrical characteristics: The electrical source is the muscle membrane potential of about -90 mV. Measured EMG potentials range between less than 50 μ V and up to 20 to 30 mV, depending on the muscle under observation.

Typical repetition rate of muscle motor unit firing is about 7–20 Hz, depending on the size of the muscle (eye muscles versus seat (gluteal) muscles), previous axonal damage and other factors. Damage to motor units can be expected at ranges between 450 and 780 mV.

2.3.2-Procedure of measuring EMG: There are two kinds of EMG in widespread use:

1. Surface EMG and
2. Intramuscular (needle and fine-wire) EMG.

Surface electrode may be used to monitor the general picture of muscle activation, as opposed to the activity of only a few fibres as observed using an intramuscular EMG. This technique is used in a number of settings; for example, in the physiotherapy clinic, muscle activation is monitored using surface EMG and patients have an auditory or visual stimulus to help them know when they are activating the muscle.

A motor unit is defined as one motor neuron and all of the muscle fibers it innervates. When a motor unit fires, the impulse (called an action potential) is carried down the motor neuron to the muscle. The area where the nerve contacts the muscle is called the neuromuscular junction, or the motor end plate. After the action potential is transmitted across the neuromuscular junction, an action potential is elicited in all of the innervated muscle fibers of that particular motor unit. The sum of all this electrical activity is known as a motor unit action potential (MUAP). This electrophysiologic activity from multiple motor units is the signal typically evaluated during an EMG. The composition of the motor unit, the number of muscle fibres per motor unit, the metabolic type of muscle fibres and many other factors affect the shape of the motor unit potentials in the myogram.

2.3.3- Electrode placement and instrumentation:

Fig- Electrode & instrumentation

Fig: wave form of normal EMG

2.4-GSR (Galvanic Skin Response) or SCR (Skin Conductivity Response)

GSR acquisition system

Low cost GSR electrode construction

Skin conductance, also known as galvanic skin response (GSR), electro-dermal response (EDR), psycho-galvanic reflex (PGR), skin conductance response (SCR) or skin conductance level (SCL), is a method of measuring the electrical conductance of the skin, which varies with its moisture level. This is of interest because the sweat glands are controlled by the sympathetic, so skin conductance is used as an indication of psychological or physiological arousal. There has been a long history of electro-dermal activity research, most of it dealing with spontaneous fluctuations or reactions to stimuli.

Section of skin from the sole of the foot. Blood vessels have been injected

Electrode on the palm for SCR

2.4.1-Description: The device measures the electrical conductance between 2 points, and is essentially a type of ohmmeter. The two paths for current are along the surface of the skin and through the body. Active measuring involves sending a small amount of current through the body.

Due to the response of the skin and muscle tissue to external and internal stimuli, the conductance can vary by several micro-Siemens. When correctly calibrated, the device can measure these subtle differences. There is a relationship between sympathetic activity and emotional arousal,

although one cannot identify which specific emotion is being elicited. The SCR is highly sensitive to emotions in some people. Fear, anger, startle response, orienting response and sexual feelings are all among the reactions which may produce similar skin conductance responses. These reactions are utilized as part of the polygraph or lie detector.

Skin conductance response in regular subjects differs when given fair and unfair offers, respectively. However, psychopaths have been shown to have no difference in skin conductance between fair and unfair offers. This may indicate that the use of lie detectors relying on skin conductivity gives psychopaths an advantage that non-psychopaths do not have in criminal investigations.

GSR test

A sample GSR signal of 60 seconds

GSR output

SCR (or GSR) is used widely in psychological research due to its cheap and effective nature. It works by measuring the sympathetic nervous systems reaction to stimuli. This means the neurotransmitter involved; unlike most ANS responses is acetylcholine, not epinephrine. The device usually measures the sweat in the palm of the hand, or sole of foot.

Abbreviations used to distinguish the type of electro-dermal measurements

Abbreviation	Significance
EDA	Electro-dermal Activity
EDL	Electro-dermal Level
EDR	Electro-dermal Response
SCL	Skin Conductance Level
SCR	Skin Conductance Response
SRL	Skin Resistance Level
SRR	Skin Resistance Response
SPL	Skin Potential Level
SPR	Skin Potential Response

2.5-Heart rate

Heart rate is the number of heartbeats per unit of time, typically expressed as *beats per minute* (bpm). Heart rate can vary as the body's need to absorb oxygen and excrete carbon dioxide changes, such as during exercise or sleep.

The measurement of heart rate is used by medical professionals to assist in the diagnosis and tracking of medical conditions. It is also used by individuals, such as athletes, who are interested in monitoring their **heart rate** to gain maximum efficiency from their training. The *R wave to R wave interval* (*RR interval*) is the inverse of the heart rate.

Commercial heart rate monitor

2.5.1- Measurement: Heart rate is measured by finding the pulse of the body. This pulse rate can be measured at any point on the body where the artery's pulsation is transmitted to the surface by pressuring it with the index and middle fingers; often it is compressed against an underlying structure like bone. The thumb should not be used for measuring another person's heart rate, as its strong pulse may interfere with correct perception of the target pulse.

Possible points for measuring the heart rate are:

1. The ventral aspect of the wrist on the side of the thumb (radial artery).
2. The ulnar artery.
3. The neck (carotid artery).
4. The inside of the elbow, or under the biceps muscle (brachial artery).
5. The groin (femoral artery).
6. Behind the medial malleolus on the feet (posterior tibial artery).

7. Middle of dorsum of the foot (dorsalis pedis).
8. Behind the knee (popliteal artery).
9. Over the abdomen (abdominal aorta).
10. The chest (apex of heart), which can be felt with one's hand or fingers. However, it is possible to auscultate the heart using a stethoscope.
11. The temple (superficial temporal artery).
12. The lateral edge of the mandible (facial artery).
13. The side of the head near the ear (basilar artery)

A more precise method of determining pulse involves the use of an electrocardiograph, or ECG (also abbreviated EKG). Continuous electrocardiograph monitoring of the heart is routinely done in many clinical settings, especially in critical care medicine. Commercial heart rate monitors are also available, consisting of a chest strap with electrodes. The signal is transmitted to a wrist receiver for display. Heart rate monitors allow accurate measurements to be taken continuously and can be used during exercise when manual measurement would be difficult or impossible (such as when the hands are being used).

2.5.2- Optical heart rate / pulse rate monitor: Most of the light is absorbed or reflected by our organs and tissues (skin, bone, muscle, blood), but some light will pass through our tissues if they are thin enough. When blood is pumped through your body, it gets squeezed into the capillary tissues, and the volume of those tissues increases very slightly. Then, between heart beats, the volume decreases. The change in volume effects the amount of light that will transmit through. This fluctuation is very small, but we can sense it with electronics. Here's how it's done.

We start with an Infrared LED, and a photodiode sensor. It's important that the two devices are matched well, so that the light wavelength output from the LED is detected strongly by the photodiode (see below for part numbers). The photodiode is essentially a teeny tiny solar cell, just like the panels on rooftops, but really small. It will generate a small voltage and current when it is blasted with photons. The Infrared LED is what we will use for our photon blaster.

IR detector & emitter

Low cost Pulse rate sensor

Sensor on bread board

2.5.3- Measurement by optical HR sensor: When we put the for-finger or ear-lobe in between the IR pair then IR transmits through finger muscles. Due to blood pumping by heart the volume of blood in finger capillaries varies, ie. There is swelling and compression if capillaries. Thus the amount of transmitted IR light changes which is detected by photodiode. Its corresponding variation gives knowledge of heart rate.

Placement of HR sensor

Graphical representation of pulse rate taken by the optical sensor

The next thing we need is a way to amplify the tiny signal coming off of the photodiode. The configuration of this circuit is well-known in analog electronics circles as a ‘Current to Voltage Converter’ and it is a classic.

2.5.4-Resting heart rate: Resting heart rate is often a good determination as to how fit you are, as well as indicating if you're either over training or unwell - showing up as unexplained increases in resting heart rate.

The typical resting heart rate in adults is 60-90 bpm, with rates below 60 bpm referred to as bradycardia, and rates above 100 bpm referred to as tachycardia.

The normal heart rate in children is variable and depends on the child's age. Children exercising can have heart rates up to 200 bpm.

The *maximum heart rate* (HR_{max}) is the highest heart rate an individual can safely achieve through exercise stress, and depends on age.

The most common formula encountered, with no indication of standard deviation, is:

$$HR_{max} = 220 - \text{age}$$

A study from Lund, Sweden gives reference values (obtained during bicycle ergometry) for men:

$$HR_{max} = 203.7 / (1 + \exp(0.033 \times (\text{age} - 104.3)))$$

and for women:

$$HR_{max} = 190.2 / (1 + \exp(0.0453 \times (\text{age} - 107.5)))$$

2.6- Pulse oximetry or SpO2

Pulse oximetry is a non-invasive method allowing the monitoring of the oxygenation of a patient's hemoglobin. It measures how much of the hemoglobin in blood is carrying oxygen (oxygen saturation).

Basic principle

Commercial pulse oximeter

The main way oxygen is carried in our blood is by means of hemoglobin. The hemoglobin without oxygen we will call deoxygenated hemoglobin (deoxy Hb). The hemoglobin with oxygen, we will call oxygenated hemoglobin (oxy Hb).

2.6.1-Physical properties used in pulse oximetry: Pulse oximetry uses light to work out oxygen saturation. Light is emitted from light sources which goes across the pulse oximeter probe and reaches the light detector. A sensor is placed on a thin part of the patient's body, usually a fingertip or earlobe, or in the case of an infant, across a foot. Light of two different wavelengths is passed through the patient to a photo detector. The changing absorbance at each of the wavelengths is measured, allowing determination of the absorbance due to the *pulsing arterial blood alone, excluding venous blood, skin, bone, muscle, fat, and (in most cases) fingernail polish*. With NIRS it is possible to measure both oxygenated and deoxygenated hemoglobin on a peripheral scale (possible on both brain and muscle).

PO uses two lights to analyze Hb

Increasing oxygen level in hemoglobin

Absorption of different wavelength by Oxy and De-oxy Hb

Tips to remember: SeXy DARLing = at SiX hundred wavelength Deoxy Absorbs Red Light

Finger Pulse Oximetry is a very important non-invasive process used to measure blood oxygen saturation levels (SpO₂) by monitoring the percentage of hemoglobin (Hb), which is saturated with oxygen as well as measuring heart rate. This procedure has been used regularly in hospitals during the past thirty years and is established as an essential measurement in medical practice, to ensure maintenance of adequate oxygen and prevention of respiratory difficulty. In many disease states, oxygen saturation is one of the most important vital signs to monitor.

SPO Medical has patented technology that uses the reflectance technique and incorporates it into portable devices that are as reliable as a thermometer or blood pressure cuff. Moreover, these devices operate at a power requirement approximately 1/50th of that compared to commercially available systems. This puts pulse oximetry into the hands medical practitioners and emergency personnel on-site for the safety and benefit of all, and offers the opportunity to create new commercial and consumer applications.

2.6.1-Near-infrared spectroscopy: Near-infrared spectroscopy (NIRS) is a spectroscopic method that uses the near-infrared region of the electromagnetic spectrum (from about 800 nm to 2500 nm). Typical applications include pharmaceutical, medical diagnostics (including blood sugar and pulse oximetry), food and agrochemical quality control, and combustion research, as well as research in functional neuro-imaging, sports medicine & science, elite sports training, ergonomics, rehabilitation, neonatal research, brain computer interface, urology (bladder contraction) and neurology (neurovascular coupling).

Near-infrared spectroscopy is based on molecular overtone and combination vibrations. Such transitions are forbidden by the selection rules of quantum mechanics. As a result, the molar absorptivity in the near IR region is typically quite small. One advantage is that NIR can typically penetrate much farther into a sample than mid infrared radiation. Near-infrared spectroscopy is, therefore, not a particularly sensitive technique, but it can be very useful in probing bulk material with little or no sample preparation.

Near IR absorption spectrum of dichloromethane showing complicated overlapping overtones of mid IR absorption features

2.7- Blood pressure

It is a kind of non-electrical bio-signal. Blood pressure (BP) is the pressure exerted by circulating blood upon the walls of blood vessels, and is one of the principal vital signs. When used without further specification, "blood pressure" usually refers to the arterial pressure of the systemic circulation. During each heartbeat, BP varies between a maximum (systolic) and a minimum (diastolic) pressure. The mean BP, due to pumping by the heart and resistance to flow in blood vessels, decreases as the circulating blood moves away from the heart through arteries. Blood pressure drops most rapidly along the small arteries and arterioles, and continues to decrease as the blood moves through the capillaries and back to the heart through veins. Gravity, valves in veins, and pumping from contraction of skeletal muscles are some other influences on BP at various places in the body.

Commercial blood pressure meter and its arrangement

2.7.1- Measurement technique: The measurement *blood pressure* without further specification usually refers to the systemic arterial pressure measured at a person's upper arm. It is measured on the inside of an elbow at the brachial artery, which is the upper arm's major blood vessel that carries blood away from the heart. A person's BP is usually expressed in terms of the systolic pressure over diastolic pressure (mmHg), for example 140/90.

Basic demonstration of BP

signal of Blood pressure with ECG

2.7.2- Classification of blood pressure for adults:

Category	systolic, mmHg	diastolic, mmHg
Hypotension	< 90	< 60
Desirable	90–119	60–79
Pre-hypertension	120–139	or 80–89
Stage 1 Hypertension	140–159	or 90–99
Stage 2 Hypertension	160–179	or 100–119
Hypertensive Crisis	≥ 180	or ≥ 120

1 year	6–9 years	adults
95/65	100/65	110/65 – 140/90

2.7.3-Mean arterial pressure: The mean arterial pressure (MAP) is the average over a cardiac cycle and is determined by the cardiac output (CO), systemic vascular resistance (SVR), and central venous pressure (CVP),

$$MAP = (CO \cdot SVR) + CVP$$

MAP can be approximately determined from measurements of the systolic pressure P_{sys} and the diastolic pressure P_{dias} while there is a normal resting heart rate,

$$MAP \approx P_{dias} + 1/3(P_{sys} - P_{dias})$$

The pulse pressure can be simply calculated from the difference of the measured systolic and diastolic pressures,

$$P_{pulse} = P_{sys} - P_{dias}$$

2.8- Body Temperature

It is also a non-electrical bio-signal. Normal human body temperature, also known as *normothermia* or *euthermia*, is a concept that depends upon the place in the body at which the measurement is made, and the time of day and level of activity of the person. There is no single number that represents a normal or healthy temperature for all people under all circumstances using any place of measurement.

Different parts of the body have different temperatures. Rectal and vaginal measurements, or measurements taken directly inside the body cavity, are typically slightly higher than oral measurements, and oral measurements are somewhat higher than skin temperature. The commonly accepted average core body temperature (taken internally) is 37.5 °C (99.5 °F). The typical oral (under the tongue) measurement is slightly cooler, at 37.0±0.5 °C, or 98.6±0.9 °F. Although some people think

of these numbers as representing the normal temperature, a wide range of temperatures has been found in healthy people. In samples of normal adult men and women, the observed range for oral temperature is 33.2–38.2 °C (92–101 °F), for rectal it is 34.4–37.8 °C (94–100 °F), for the tympanic cavity it is 35.4–37.8 °C (96–100 °F) and for auxiliary it is 35.5–37.0 °C (96–99 °F).

A temperature set point is the level at which the body attempts to maintain its temperature. When the set point is raised, the result is a fever. Most fevers are caused by infectious disease and can be lowered, if desired, with antipyretic medications.

comm..thermometer

thermal response during work and rest

2.9- Signal Amplification & Signal processing:

Since potential generated by muscles and neurons are of microvolt or millivolt range so to amplify it with less noise is a too tough task. For amplification here we use different instrumentation amplifier in place of normal op-amp because these in-amps require very low input voltage and then amplify it significantly. To get the high S/N ratio we have to amplify it and then apply recent logics for artifact and different noise removal. On hardware basis we implement different filters with sensors for some band removal or taking some specified band out of all.

2.10-Variations in bio-signals & Need of real time integrated data acquisition system:

The variation has been seeing in different electrical and non-electrical bio-signals by cognitive enhancement, meditation, emotion, workload and other events. So for the acquisition of bio-signals for study and analysis we have firstly to bring the person at the place where the facilities are. Then we have to develop the environment like game, virtual war situation etc for study and analysis which is not accurate as in the actual situation.

So if we have a suite implanted with many sensors for different sensors along with a single signal acquisition system with ability to transmit data wirelessly then we'll able to study more accurately and can get data in real time for cognitive, medical and other analysis.

3.1- Hardware: The main hardware instruments used here are sensors, electrodes, IR emitter, detector, instrumentation amplifier, filter, microcontroller board, Bluetooth etc.

3.1.1- Sensors- A sensor (also called detectors) is a device that measures a measurable attribute and converts it into a signal which can be read by an observer or by an instrument.

3.1.1.1- Smart Sensor- A smart sensor is a sensor , in addition to the actual measured value capturing the full range of signal processing and signal processing in one housing. It is a device that measures a signal or signals, processes data from the signal(s), and seamlessly integrates with wireless networks to transmit the data. Such sensors often contain complex including a microcontroller , if necessary, with additional DSP functionality and features similar more complex logic devices such as FPGAs , ...and standardized interfaces are ready to communicate with host systems, eg via field bus systems , sensor networks .

CMOS APS developed by NASA

The technological basis for ensuring that such complex intelligent sensors can be realized in miniature form as such offer, including the micro-technology , micro systems technology and nanotechnology .

Smart sensors with different interfaces to be equipped, wired, optical non-contact inductive coupling or pipe via passive and active radio techniques,

In health care, such sensors are used in real-time monitoring of a variety of parameters (movement, temperature, blood pressure, oxygen and glucose levels, heart rate, etc) and medication compliance.

3.1.1.2- Wearable sensors and systems have evolved to the point that they can be considered ready for clinical application. The use of wearable monitoring devices that allow continuous or intermittent monitoring of physiological signals is critical for the advancement of both the diagnosis as well as treatment of diseases. Wearable systems are totally non-obtrusive devices that

allow physicians to overcome the limitations of ambulatory technology and provide a response to the need for monitoring individuals over weeks or months.

3.1.2- Electrodes: Electrode is an electrical conductor used to make contact with a nonmetallic part of a circuit. Here in bio-signal acquisition the electrodes are used to make a metal contact with skin. Here a special type of silver chloride gel/paste is used to reduce the impedance.

The electrode and gel used in this work are:

Electrode, gel and cable for ECG, EEG and EMG with gel application

3.1.3- IR emitter & detector:

Infrared (IR) light is electromagnetic radiation with a wavelength longer than that of visible light, measured from the nominal edge of visible red light at 0.74 micro-metres (μm), and extending conventionally to 300 μm . These wavelengths correspond to a frequency range of approximately 1 to 400 THz,^[1] and include most of the thermal radiation emitted by objects near room temperature. Microscopically, IR light is typically emitted or absorbed by molecules when they change their rotational-vibrational movements.

<i>Ultraviolet</i>	<i>10 nm - 390 nm</i>	<i>30 EHz - 790 THz</i>	<i>3 eV to 124 eV</i>
<i>Visible</i>	<i>390 - 750 nm</i>	<i>790 THz - 405 THz</i>	<i>1.7 eV - 3.3 eV</i>
<i>Infrared</i>	<i>750 nm - 1 mm</i>	<i>405 THz - 300 GHz</i>	<i>1.24 meV - 1.7 eV</i>

Infrared light is used in industrial, scientific, and medical applications. It can observe changing blood flow in the skin.

An **infrared emitter** (IR-LED) is a type of electronic device that emits infrared light not visible to the naked eye. An infrared LED operates like a regular LED, but may use different materials to produce infrared light.

An infrared LED is, like all LEDs, a type of diode, or simple semiconductor. The wavelength and color of the light produced depend on the material used in the diode. Infrared LEDs use material that produces light in the infrared part of the spectrum, that is, just below what the human

eye can see. Different infrared LEDs may produce infrared light of differing wavelengths, just like different LEDs produce light of different colors..

IR emitter detector

An infrared detector is a photocell like device which generates current according to light. The reverse-bias operation is another popular use for the photodiode. This operation allows the photodiode to be used as a light intensity-to-voltage transducer. Here is the common schematic symbol for a photodiode and some typical photodiode packages.

3.1.4- Instrumentation Amplifier: An instrumentation amplifier is a type of differential amplifier that has been outfitted with input buffers, which eliminate the need for input impedance matching and thus make the amplifier particularly suitable for use in measurement and test equipment. Additional characteristics include very low DC offset, low drift, low noise, very high open-loop gain, very high common-mode rejection ratio, and very high input impedances. Instrumentation amplifiers are used where great accuracy and stability of the circuit both short- and long-term are required.

The most commonly used instrumentation amplifier circuit is shown in the figure. The gain of the circuit is given

Typical instrumentation amplifier schematic

$$\frac{V_{out}}{V_2 - V_1} = \left(1 + \frac{2R_1}{R_{gain}}\right) \frac{R_3}{R_2}$$

gain of the in-amp circuit

Instrumentation amplifiers (in-amps) amplify the difference between two signals. These differential signals typically emanate from sensors.

The rightmost amplifier, along with the resistors labeled R_2 and R_3 is just the standard differential amplifier circuit, with gain = R_3 / R_2 and differential input resistance = $2 \cdot R_2$. The two amplifiers on the left are the buffers. With R_{gain} removed (open circuited), they are simple unity gain buffers; the circuit

will work in that state, with gain simply equal to R_3 / R_2 and high input impedance because of the buffers. The buffer gain could be increased by putting resistors between the buffer inverting inputs and ground to shunt away some of the negative feedback; however, the single resistor R_{gain} between the two inverting inputs is a much more elegant method: it increases the differential-mode gain of the buffer pair while leaving the common-mode gain equal to 1. This increases the common-mode rejection ratio (CMRR) of the circuit and also enables the buffers to handle much larger common-mode signals without clipping than would be the case if they were separate and had the same gain. Another benefit of the method is that it boosts the gain using a single resistor rather than a pair, thus avoiding a resistor-matching problem (although the two R_1 s need to be matched), and very conveniently allowing the gain of the circuit to be changed by changing the value of a single resistor. A set of switch-selectable resistors or even a potentiometer can be used for R_{gain} , providing easy changes to the gain of the circuit, without the complexity of having to switch matched pairs of resistors.

3.1.4.1- AD624AD In-amp. –The AD624 is a high precision, low noise, instrumentation amplifier designed primarily for use with low level transducers, including load cells, strain gauges and pressure transducers. An outstanding combination of low noise, high gain accuracy, low gain temperature coefficient and high linearity make the AD624 ideal for use in high resolution data acquisition systems.

- IC, IN-AMP, DIP16, 624
- No. of Amplifiers: 1
- Input Offset Voltage: 200 μ V
- Gain dB Min: 1dB
- Bandwidth: 25MHz
- Amplifier Output: Single Ended
- CMRR: 130dB
- Slew Rate: 5V/ μ s
- Supply Voltage Range: $\pm$ 6V to $\pm$ 18V
- Supply Current: 3.5mA
- Amplifier Case Style: DIP
- No. of Pins: 16
- Operate Temp Range: -25 $^{\circ}$ C to +85 $^{\circ}$ C
- Amplifier Type: Instrumentation
- Base Number: 624
- Gain Bandwidth: 1MHz
- IC Generic Number: 624
- Input Offset Drift Max: 0.25 μ V/ $^{\circ}$ C
- Input Offset Voltage Max: 200 μ V
- Logic Function Number: 624
- Operating Temperature Max: 85 $^{\circ}$ C
- Operating Temperature Min: -25 $^{\circ}$ C
- Op- Amplifier Features: Low Noise
- Output Type: Single Ended
- Package / Case: DIP
- Programmable Gain Max: 1000
- Programmable Gain Min: 1
- Slew Rate: 5
- Supply Voltage + Nom: 15V
- Supply Voltage Max: 18V
- Supply Voltage Min: 6V
- Termination Type: Through Hole

AD624AD

FUNCTIONAL BLOCK DIAGRAM

In-amp AD624AD and its functional diagram

3.1.4.5- INA128P- The INA128 and INA129 are low power, general purpose instrumentation amplifiers offering excellent accuracy. The versatile 3-op amp design and small size make them ideal for a wide range of applications. Current-feedback input circuitry provides wide bandwidth even at high gain (200 kHz at G = 100).

A single external resistor sets any gain from 1 to 10,000. The INA128 provides an industry-standard gain equation. The INA128/INA129 is laser trimmed for very low offset voltage (50μV), drift (0.5μV/°C) and high common-mode rejection (120dB at G ≥ 100). It operates with power supplies as low as ±2.25V, and quiescent current is only 700μA—ideal for battery operated systems. Internal input protection can withstand up to ±40V without damage. The INA128/INA129 is available in 8-pin plastic DIP and SO-8 surface-mount packages, specified for the -40°C to +85°C temperature range. The INA128 is also available in a dual configuration, the INA2128.

Instrumentation amplifier INA128P – IC, internal circuit and pin description

➤ **FEATURES**

- **LOW OFFSET VOLTAGE:** 50µV max
- **LOW DRIFT:** 0.5µV/°C max
- **LOW INPUT BIAS CURRENT:** 5nA max
- **HIGH CMR:** 120dB min
- **INPUTS PROTECTED TO ±40V**
- **WIDE SUPPLY RANGE:** ±2.25V to±18V
- **LOW QUIESCENT CURRENT:** 700µA
- **8-PIN PLASTIC DIP, SO-8**

➤ **APPLICATIONS**

- **BRIDGE AMPLIFIER**
- **THERMOCOUPLE AMPLIFIER**
- **RTD SENSOR AMPLIFIER**
- **MEDICAL INSTRUMENTATION**
- **DATA ACQUISITION**

4.1.4.6- INA114 In-amp- The INA114 is a low cost, general purpose instrumentation amplifier offering excellent accuracy. Its versatile 3-op amp design and small size make it ideal for a wide range of applications. A single external resistor sets any gain from 1 to 10,000. Internal input protection can withstand up to ±40V without damage. The INA114 is laser trimmed for very low offset voltage (50mV), drift (0.25mV/°C) and high common-mode rejection (115dB at G = 1000). It operates with power supplies as low as ±2.25V, allowing use in battery operated and single 5V supply systems. Quiescent current is 3mA maximum. The INA114 is available in 8-pin plastic and SOL-16 surface-mount packages. Both are specified for the -40°C to +85°C temperature range.

Instrumentation amplifier INA128P – IC, internal circuit and pin description

FEATURES

- LOW OFFSET VOLTAGE: 50mV max
- LOW DRIFT: 0.25mV/°C max
- LOW INPUT BIAS CURRENT: 2nA max
- HIGH COMMON-MODE REJECTION: 115dB min
- INPUT OVER-VOLTAGE PROTECTION: ±40V
- 1 WIDE SUPPLY RANGE: ±2.25 to ±18V
- LOW QUIESCENT CURRENT: 3mA max
- 8-PIN PLASTIC AND SOL-16

APPLICATIONS

- BRIDGE AMPLIFIER
- THERMOCOUPLE AMPLIFIER
- RTD SENSOR AMPLIFIER
- MEDICAL INSTRUMENTATION
- DATA ACQUISITION

4.1.4.7- MCP 6002 Op-amp- The MCP6002 is a dual general purpose op amp offering rail-to-rail input and output over the 1.8 to 6V operating range. This amplifier has a typical GBWP of 1 MHz with typical quiescent current of 100 microamperes. The MCP6002 is available in 8-lead PDIP, SOIC and MSOP packages. Mounting Type: Through Hole Number of Pins: 8

Typical Application

Specifications:

- Amplifier Type: Operational
- Bandwidth: 1 MHz
- Base Number: 6002
- Gain Bandwidth: 1 MHz
- I/O Type: Rail-Rail I/O
- Input Offset Voltage Max: 0 mV
- Number of Amplifiers: 2
- Op Amp Type: General Purpose
- Operating Temp Range: -40°C to +125°C
- Package / Case: DIP
- SVHC: No SVHC (15-Dec-2010)
- Slew Rate: 0.6 V/μs
- Supply Voltage + Nom: 5.5 V

- Supply Voltage Range: 1.8 V to 5.5 V

3.1.5-Electronic filters: Electronic filters are electronic circuits which perform signal processing functions, specifically to remove unwanted frequency components from the signal, to enhance wanted ones, or both

In signal processing, a filter is a device or process that removes from a signal some unwanted component or feature. Filtering is a class of signal processing, the defining feature of filters being the complete or partial suppression of some aspect of the signal. Most often, this means removing some frequencies and not others in order to suppress interfering signals and reduce background noise. However, filters do not exclusively act in the frequency domain; especially in the field of image processing many other targets for filtering exist.

The drawback of filtering is the loss of information associated with it. Signal combination in Fourier space is an alternative approach for removal of certain frequencies from the recorded signal.

Some signal processing filters are:

3.1.5.1-Low-pass filter: A low-pass filter is an electronic filter that passes low-frequency signals but attenuates (reduces the amplitude of) signals with frequencies higher than the cutoff frequency. The actual amount of attenuation for each frequency varies from filter to filter

Passive, first order low-pass RC filter

Algorithmic implementation: The filter recurrence relation provides a way to determine the output samples in terms of the input samples and the preceding output. The following pseudocode algorithm will simulate the effect of a low-pass filter on a series of digital samples:

// Return RC low-pass filter output samples, given input samples,

// time interval dt, and time constant RC

function lowpass(real[0..n] x, real dt, real RC)

var real[0..n] y

var real $\alpha = dt / (RC + dt)$

y[0] := x[0]

for i from 1 to n

$$y[i] = \alpha * x[i] + (1-\alpha) * y[i-1]$$

return y

The loop that calculates each of the n outputs can be refactored into the equivalent:

for i from 1 to n

$$y[i] = y[i-1] + \alpha * (x[i] - y[i-1])$$

3.1.5.2- High-pass filter- A high-pass filter (HPF) is a device that passes high frequencies and attenuates (i.e., reduces the amplitude of) frequencies lower than its cutoff frequency. A high-pass filter is usually modeled as a linear time-invariant system.

High-pass filters have many uses, such as blocking DC from circuitry sensitive to non-zero average voltages or RF devices. They can also be used in conjunction with a low-pass filter to make a band-pass filter. The actual amount of attenuation for each frequency is a design parameter of the filter

A passive, analog, first-order high-pass filter

Algorithmic implementation: The filter recurrence relation provides a way to determine the output samples in terms of the input samples and the preceding output. The following pseudo-code algorithm will simulate the effect of a high-pass filter on a series of digital samples:

// Return RC high-pass filter output samples, given input samples,

// time interval dt, and time constant RC

function highpass(real[0..n] x, real dt, real RC)

var real[0..n] y

var real $\alpha := RC / (RC + dt)$

y[0] := x[0]

for i from 1 to n

*y[i] := $\alpha * y[i-1] + \alpha * (x[i] - x[i-1])$*

return y

The loop which calculates each of the n outputs can be refactored into the equivalent:

for i from 1 to n

$$y[i] := \alpha * (y[i-1] + x[i] - x[i-1])$$

3.1.5.3-Band-pass filter: A **band-pass filter** is a device that passes frequencies within a certain range and rejects (attenuates) frequencies outside that range.

A medium-complexity example of a band-Pass filter

Response of band-pass filter

3.1.5.4-Band-stop filter: In signal processing, a band-stop filter or band-rejection filter is a filter that passes most frequencies unaltered, but attenuates those in a specific range to very low levels. It is the opposite of a band-pass filter. A **notch filter** is a band-stop filter with a narrow stop band (high Q factor).

A generic ideal band-stop filter, showing both positive and negative angular frequencies

band-stop filter

3.1.5.5-Notch filter: A Notch filter is a filter that passes all frequencies except those in a stop band centered on a center frequency. A closely related Knowledgebase item discusses the concept of the Q of a filter. This Knowledgebase item focuses on high Q notch filters - the type that eliminate a single frequency or narrow band of frequencies. A closely related type of filter - a band reject filter, is discussed in a separate knowledgebase item. The amplitude response of a notch filter is flat at all frequencies except for the stop band on either side of the the center frequency. The standard reference

points for the roll-offs on each side of the stop band are the points where the amplitude has decreased by 3 dB, to 70.7% of its original amplitude.

A typical notch filter

Response of notch filter

3.1.6- Signal Processing: The digitization process is the first and most important step in signal processing. In this process firstly the analog output of sensor is digitized. Here this step is done by my Arduino Mega 2560 board upto a limit. For more processing we use many tools like Processing programming, Matlab, LabVIEW and others.

3.1.7-Arduino Mega 2560 Rev3 Data Acquisition Board:

4.1.7.1-Overview- The Arduino Mega 2560 is a microcontroller board based on the ATmega2560 microcontroller which has 100 pins. This board has 54 digital input/output pins (of which 14 can be used as PWM outputs), 16 analog inputs, 4 UARTs (hardware serial ports), a 16 MHz crystal oscillator, a USB connection, a power jack, an ICSP header, and a reset button. It contains everything needed to support the microcontroller; simply connect it to a computer with a USB cable or power it with a AC-to-DC adapter or battery to get started. The Mega is compatible with most shields sensors or sensor implement board designed for the Arduino Duemilanove or Diecimila which are previous boards of arduino series.

Arduino Mega 2560 R3 Front

Arduino Mega2560 R3 Back

The above two figures are front and back view of Arduino Mega 2560 Rev3 board.

3.1.7.2-Schematic, Reference Design- arduino-mega2560:

Arduino Mega 2560 Reference Design

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The Arduino Mega 2560 Reference Design is a reference design for the Arduino Mega 2560. It is a complete circuit board that includes all the components needed to run the Arduino Mega 2560. The design is based on the Arduino Mega 2560 Rev. 3.0.0. The design is a reference design and is not intended to be used as a final design. It is intended to be used as a starting point for your own design.

3.1.7.3- ATmega2560-Arduino Pin Mapping: Below is the pin mapping for the Atmega2560. The chip used in Arduino 2560.

3.1.7.4- Arduino Mega 2560 PIN mapping table:

Pin Number	Pin Name	Mapped Pin Name
1	PG5 (OC0B)	Digital pin 4 (PWM)
2	PE0 (RXD0/PCINT8)	Digital pin 0 (PWM) (RX0)
3	PE1 (TXD0)	Digital pin 1 (PWM) (TX0)
4	PE2 (XCK0/AIN0)	
5	PE3 (OC3A/AIN1)	Digital pin 5 (PWM)
6	PE4 (OC3B/INT4)	Digital pin 2 (PWM)
7	PE5 (OC3C/INT5)	Digital pin 3 (PWM)
8	PE6 (T3/INT6)	
9	PE7 (CLK0/ICP3/INT7)	
10	VCC	VCC
11	GND	GND
12	PH0 (RXD2)	Digital pin 17 (PWM)
13	PH1 (TXD2)	Digital pin 16 (PWM)
14	PH2 (XCK2)	(TX3)
15	PH3 (OC4A)	Digital pin 6 (PWM)(RX3)
16	PH4 (OC4B)	Digital pin 7 (PWM)(TX2)
17	PH5 (OC4C)	Digital pin 8 (PWM)(RX2)
18	PH6 (OC2B)	Digital pin 9 (PWM)(TX1)
19	PB0 (SS/PCINT0)	Digital pin 53 (PWM)(RX1)
20	PB1 (SCK/PCINT1)	Digital pin 52 (PWM)(SDA)
21	PB2 (MOSI/PCINT2)	Digital pin 51 (PWM)(SCL)
22	PB3 (MISO/PCINT3)	Digital pin 50
23	PB4 (OC2A/PCINT4)	Digital pin 10 (PWM)
24	PB5 (OC1A/PCINT5)	Digital pin 11 (PWM)
25	PB6 (OC1B/PCINT6)	Digital pin 12 (PWM)
26	PB7 (OC0A/OC1C/PCINT7)	Digital pin 13 (PWM)
27	PH7 (T4)	
28	PG3 (TOSC2)	
29	PG4 (TOSC1)	
30	RESET	RESET
31	VCC	VCC
32	GND	GND

33	XTAL2	XTAL2
34	XTAL1	XTAL1
35	PL0 (ICP4)	Digital pin 49
36	PL1 (ICP5)	Digital pin 48
37	PL2 (T5)	Digital pin 47
38	PL3 (OC5A)	Digital pin 46 (PWM)
39	PL4 (OC5B)	Digital pin 45 (PWM)
40	PL5 (OC5C)	Digital pin 44 (PWM)
41	PL6	Digital pin 43
42	PL7	Digital pin 42
43	PD0 (SCL/INT0)	Digital pin 21 (SCL)
44	PD1 (SDA/INT1)	Digital pin 20 (SDA)
45	PD2 (RXDI/INT2)	Digital pin 19
46	PD3 (TXD1/INT3)	Digital pin 18
47	PD4 (ICP1)	
48	PD5 (XCK1)	
49	PD6 (T1)	
50	PD7 (T0)	Digital pin 38
51	PG0 (WR)	Digital pin 41
52	PG1 (RD)	Digital pin 40
53	PC0 (A8)	Digital pin 37
54	PC1 (A9)	Digital pin 36
55	PC2 (A10)	Digital pin 35
56	PC3 (A11)	Digital pin 34
57	PC4 (A12)	Digital pin 33
58	PC5 (A13)	Digital pin 32
59	PC6 (A14)	Digital pin 31
60	PC7 (A15)	Digital pin 30
61	VCC	VCC
62	GND	GND
63	PJ0 (RXD3/PCINT9)	Digital pin 15
64	PJ1 (TXD3/PCINT10)	Digital pin 14
65	PJ2 (XCK3/PCINT11)	
66	PJ3 (PCINT12)	

67	PJ4 (PCINT13)	
68	PJ5 (PCINT14)	
69	PJ6 (PCINT 15)	
70	PG2 (ALE)	Digital pin 39
71	PA7 (AD7)	Digital pin 29
72	PA6 (AD6)	Digital pin 28
73	PA5 (AD5)	Digital pin 27
74	PA4 (AD4)	Digital pin 26
75	PA3 (AD3)	Digital pin 25
76	PA2 (AD2)	Digital pin 24
77	PA1 (AD1)	Digital pin 23
78	PA0 (AD0)	Digital pin 22
79	PJ7	
80	VCC	VCC
81	GND	GND
82	PK7 (ADC15/PCINT23)	Analog pin 15
83	PK6 (ADC14/PCINT22)	Analog pin 14
84	PK5 (ADC13/PCINT21)	Analog pin 13
85	PK4 (ADC12/PCINT20)	Analog pin 12
86	PK3 (ADC11/PCINT19)	Analog pin 11
87	PK2 (ADC10/PCINT18)	Analog pin 10
88	PK1 (ADC9/PCINT17)	Analog pin 9
89	PK0 (ADC8/PCINT16)	Analog pin 8
90	PF7 (ADC7/PCINT15)	Analog pin 7
91	PF6 (ADC6/PCINT14)	Analog pin 6
92	PF5 (ADC5/TMS)	Analog pin 5
93	PF4 (ADC4/TMK)	Analog pin 4
94	PF3 (ADC3)	Analog pin 3
95	PF2 (ADC2)	Analog pin 2
96	PF1 (ADC1)	Analog pin 1
97	PF0 (ADC0)	Analog pin 0
98	AREF	Analog Reference
99	GND	GND
100	AVCC	VCC

3.1.7.5- Advantage to use Arduino Mega 2560 board: The most important reason to use this board here is its light weight. Since this work is on wearable sensor suite so the weight must be as least as possible. I think this board is the lightest and smallest acquisition board of the world available till now(see weight and shape in summary) very high speed microcontroller. It has 54 I/O pins to make this DAQ board multi-channel and thus to use more sensors. Other than these reasons this board is open source so most of the sensors available or handmade are compatible with it.

3.1.7.6- Summary & pin details:

Microcontroller	ATmega2560
Operating Voltage	5V
Input Voltage (recommended)	7-12V
Input Voltage (limits)	6-20V
Digital I/O Pins	54 (of which 14 provide PWM output)
Analog Input Pins	16
DC Current per I/O Pin	40 mA
DC Current for 3.3V Pin	50 mA
Flash Memory	256 KB of which 8 KB used by boot loader
SRAM	8 KB
EEPROM	4 KB
Clock Speed	16 MHz
Weight	34.9 gm
Length	101.98 mm
Width	53.63 mm
Height	15.29 mm

- **1.0 pinout:** added SDA and SCL pins that are near to the AREF pin and two other new pins placed near to the RESET pin, the IOREF that allow the shields to adapt to the voltage provided from the board. In future, shields will be compatible both with the board that use the AVR, which operate with 5V and with the Arduino Due that operate with 3.3V. The second one is a not connected pin, that is reserved for future purposes.
- Stronger RESET circuit.
- Atmega 16U2 replace the 8U2.

The power pins are as follows:

- **VIN.** The input voltage to the Arduino board when it's using an external power source (as opposed to 5 volts from the USB connection or other regulated power source). You can supply voltage through this pin, or, if supplying voltage via the power jack, access it through this pin.

- **5V.** The regulated power supply used to power the microcontroller and other components on the board. This can come either from VIN via an on-board regulator, or be supplied by USB or another regulated 5V supply.
- **3V3.** A 3.3 volt supply generated by the on-board regulator. Maximum current draw is 50 mA.
- **GND.** Ground pins.

Memory

The ATmega2560 has 256 KB of flash memory for storing code (of which 8 KB is used for the boot loader), 8 KB of SRAM and 4 KB of EEPROM (which can be read and written with the EEPROM library).

EEPROM Library

The microcontroller on the Arduino board has EEPROM: memory whose values are kept when the board is turned off (like a tiny hard drive). This library enables you to read and write those bytes.

The microcontrollers on the various Arduino boards have different amounts of EEPROM: 1024 bytes on the ATmega328, 512 bytes on the ATmega168 and ATmega8, 4KB (4096 bytes) on the ATmega1280 and ATmega2560.

3.1.7.6- Functions:

- *read()* - Reads a byte from the EEPROM. Locations that have never been written to have the value of 255.

EEPROM.read (address)

Example

```
#include <EEPROM.h>
```

```
int a = 0;
```

```
int value;
```

```
void setup()
```

```
{
```

```
  Serial.begin(9600);
```

```
}
```

```
void loop()
```

```
{
```

```
  value = EEPROM.read(a);
```

```
  Serial.print(a);
```

```
  Serial.print("\t");
```

```
  Serial.print(value);
```

```
  Serial.println();
```

```
  a = a + 1;
```

```
if (a == 512)
  a = 0;

delay(500);
}
```

- **write()** - Write a byte to the EEPROM.

```
EEPROM.write(address, value)
```

Note: An EEPROM write takes 3.3 ms to complete. The EEPROM memory has a specified life of 100,000 write/erase cycles, so you may need to be careful about how often you write to it.

Example

```
#include <EEPROM.h>

void setup()
{
  for (int i = 0; i < 512; i++)
    EEPROM.write(i, i);
}

void loop()
{
}
```

Input and Output: Each of the 54 digital pins on the Mega can be used as an input or output, using `pinMode()`, `digitalWrite()` and `digitalRead()` functions. They operate at 5 volts. Each pin can provide or receive a maximum of 40 mA and has an internal pull-up resistor (disconnected by default) of 20-50 kOhms.

- **pinMode()** - Configures the specified pin to behave either as an input or an output. See the description of digital pins for details.

```
pinMode(pin, mode)
```

Example

```
int ledPin = 13;           // LED connected to digital pin 13

void setup()
{
  pinMode(ledPin, OUTPUT); // sets the digital pin as output
}
```

```

void loop()
{
  digitalWrite(ledPin, HIGH); // sets the LED on
  delay(1000);                // waits for a second
  digitalWrite(ledPin, LOW);  // sets the LED off
  delay(1000);                // waits for a second
}

```

Note: The analog input pins can be used as digital pins, referred to as A0, A1, etc.

- **digitalWrite()** - Write a HIGH or a LOW value to a digital pin. If the pin has been configured as an OUTPUT with `pinMode()`, its voltage will be set to the corresponding value: 5V (or 3.3V on 3.3V boards) for HIGH, 0V (ground) for LOW.

digitalWrite(pin, value)

Example

```

int ledPin = 13;           // LED connected to digital pin 13
void setup()
{
  pinMode(ledPin, OUTPUT); // sets the digital pin as output
}

void loop()
{
  digitalWrite(ledPin, HIGH); // sets the LED on
  delay(1000);                // waits for a second
  digitalWrite(ledPin, LOW);  // sets the LED off
  delay(1000);                // waits for a second
}

```

Sets pin 13 to HIGH, makes a one-second-long delay, and sets the pin back to LOW.

Note: The analog input pins can be used as digital pins, referred to as A0, A1, etc.

- **digitalRead()** - Reads the value from a specified digital pin, either HIGH or LOW.

digitalRead(pin)

Example

```

int ledPin = 13; // LED connected to digital pin 13
int inPin = 7;   // pushbutton connected to digital pin 7
int val = 0;    // variable to store the read value

void setup()
{
  pinMode(ledPin, OUTPUT); // sets the digital pin 13 as output
  pinMode(inPin, INPUT);   // sets the digital pin 7 as input
}

```

```

}

void loop()
{
  val = digitalRead(inPin); // read the input pin
  digitalWrite(ledPin, val); // sets the LED to the button's value
}

```

Sets pin 13 to the same value as the pin 7, which is an input.

Note: If the pin isn't connected to anything, `digitalRead()` can return either HIGH or LOW (and this can change randomly).

The analog input pins can be used as digital pins, referred to as A0, A1, etc.

3.1.7.7 - Constants - Constants are predefined variables in the Arduino language. They are used to make the programs easier to read. We classify constants in groups.

➤ **Defining Logical Levels, true and false (Boolean Constants)**

There are two constants used to represent truth and falsity in the Arduino language: **true**, and **false**.

➤ **Defining Pin Levels, HIGH and LOW**

When reading or writing to a digital pin there are only two possible values a pin can take/be-set to: *HIGH and LOW*.

➤ **Defining Digital Pins, INPUT and OUTPUT**

Digital pins can be used either as *INPUT* or *OUTPUT*. Changing a pin from INPUT TO OUTPUT with `pinMode()` drastically changes the electrical behavior of the pin.

➤ **Pins Configured as Inputs**

Arduino (Atmega) pins configured as *INPUT* with `pinMode()` are said to be in a high-impedance state. This makes them useful for reading a sensor, but not powering an LED.

➤ **Pins Configured as Outputs**

Pins configured as *OUTPUT* with `pinMode()` are said to be in a low-impedance state. The amount of current provided by an Atmega pin is also not enough to power most relays or motors, and some interface circuitry will be required.

3.1.7.8- In addition, some pins have specialized functions:

- **Serial: 0 (RX) and 1 (TX); Serial 1: 19 (RX) and 18 (TX); Serial 2: 17 (RX) and 16 (TX); Serial 3: 15 (RX) and 14 (TX).** Used to receive (RX) and transmit (TX) TTL serial data. Pins 0 and 1 are also

connected to the corresponding pins of the ATmega16U2 USB-to-TTL Serial chip.

- **External Interrupts: 2 (interrupt 0), 3 (interrupt 1), 18 (interrupt 5), 19 (interrupt 4), 20 (interrupt 3), and 21 (interrupt 2).** These pins can be configured to trigger an interrupt on a low value, a rising or falling edge, or a change in value.

3.1.7.9- PWM: PWM, is a technique for getting analog results with digital means. The duration of "on time" is called the pulse width. To get varying analog values, you change, or modulate, that pulse width. If you repeat this on-off pattern fast enough with an.

In the graphic below, the green lines represent a regular time period. This duration or period is the inverse of the PWM frequency. In other words, with Arduino's PWM frequency at about 500Hz, the green lines would measure 2 milliseconds each. A call to *analogWrite()* is on a scale of 0 - 255, such that *analogWrite(255)* requests a 100% duty cycle (always on), and *analogWrite(127)* is a 50% duty cycle (on half the time) for example.

Pin 0 to 13. Provide 8-bit PWM output with the *analogWrite()* function.

analogWrite() - Writes an analog value (PWM wave) to a pin. Can be used to light a LED at varying brightnesses or drive a motor at various speeds. After a call to *analogWrite()*, the pin will generate a steady square wave of the specified duty cycle until the next call to *analogWrite()* (or a call to *digitalRead()* or *digitalWrite()* on the same pin). The frequency of the PWM signal is approximately 490 Hz.

analogWrite(pin, value)

Example: Sets the output to the LED proportional to the value read from the potentiometer.

```
int ledPin = 9; // LED connected to digital pin 9
int analogPin = 3; // potentiometer connected to analog pin 3
int val = 0; // variable to store the read value

void setup()
{
  pinMode(ledPin, OUTPUT); // sets the pin as output
}

void loop()
{
  val = analogRead(analogPin); // read the input pin
  analogWrite(ledPin, val / 4); // analogRead values go from 0 to 1023, analogWrite values from 0 to 255
}
```

- **analogRead()** - Reads the value from the specified analog pin. The Arduino board contains a 6 channel (8 channels on the Mini and Nano, 16 on the Mega), 10-bit analog to digital converter. This means that it will map input voltages between 0 and 5 volts into integer values between 0 and 1023. This yields a resolution between readings of: 5 volts / 1024 units or, .0049 volts (4.9 mV) per unit. The input range and resolution can be changed using *analogReference()*.

It takes about 100 microseconds (0.0001 s) to read an analog input, so the maximum reading rate is about 10,000 times a second.

analogRead(pin)

Example

```
int analogPin = 3; // potentiometer wiper (middle terminal) connected to analog pin 3
// outside leads to ground and +5V
int val = 0; // variable to store the value read

void setup()
{
  Serial.begin(9600); // setup serial
}

void loop()
{
  val = analogRead(analogPin); // read the input pin
  Serial.println(val); // debug value
}
```

3.1.7.10- SPI library: This library allows you to communicate with SPI devices, with the Arduino as the master device. *SPI: 50 (MISO), 51 (MOSI), 52 (SCK), 53 (SS).* These pins support SPI

communication using the SPI library. The SPI pins are also broken out on the ICSP header, which is physically compatible with the Uno, Duemilanove and Diecimila.

Serial Peripheral Interface (SPI) is a synchronous serial data protocol used by microcontrollers for communicating with one or more peripheral devices quickly over short distances. It can also be used for communication between two microcontrollers.

With an SPI connection there is always one master device (usually a microcontroller) which controls the peripheral devices. Typically there are three lines common to all the devices,

- Master In Slave Out (MISO) - The Slave line for sending data to the master,
- Master Out Slave In (MOSI) - The Master line for sending data to the peripherals,
- Serial Clock (SCK) - The clock pulses which synchronize data transmission generated by the master, and
- Slave Select pin - the pin on each device that the master can use to enable and disable specific devices. This allows you to have multiple SPI devices sharing the same MISO, MOSI, and CLK lines.

The SPI standard is loose and each device implements it a little differently. The SPI. `setDataMode()` function lets you set the mode to control clock polarity and phase according to this table:

Mode	Clock Polarity (CPOL)	Clock Phase (CPHA)
0	0	0
1	0	1
2	1	0
3	1	1

3.1.7.11- Connections: On the Arduino Mega, the SPI bus uses pins 50 (MISO), 51 (MOSI), 52 (SCK), and 53 (SS). Note that even if you're not using the SS pin, it must remain set as an output; otherwise, the SPI interface can be put into slave mode, rendering the library inoperative.

It is possible to use a pin other than pin 10 as the slave select (SS) pin. For example, the Arduino Ethernet shield uses pin 4 to control the SPI connection to the on-board SD card, and pin 10 to control the connection to the Ethernet controller.

3.1.7.12- Functions for SPI interface:

- **begin()** - Initializes the SPI bus, setting SCK, MOSI, and SS to outputs, pulling SCK and MOSI low and SS high.

SPI.begin()

- **end()** -Disables the SPI bus (leaving pin modes unchanged).

SPI.end()

- **setBitOrder()** - Sets the order of the bits shifted out of and into the SPI bus, either LSBFIRST (least-significant bit first) or MSBFIRST (most-significant bit first).

SPI.setBitOrder(order)

- **setClockDivider()** - Sets the SPI clock divider relative to the system clock. The dividers available are 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64, or 128. The default setting is SPI_CLOCK_DIV4, which sets the SPI clock to one-quarter the frequency of the system clock.

SPI.setClockDivider(divider)

3.1.7.13- Programming Language Reference: Arduino programs can be divided in three main parts: *structure*, *values* (variables and constants), and *functions*.

Structure	Variables	Functions
<i>setup()</i> <i>loop()</i>	Constants	Digital I/O
Control Structures	<i>HIGH LOW</i> <i>INPUT OUTPUT</i> <i>true false</i> <i>integer constants</i> <i>floating point constants</i>	<i>pinMode()</i> <i>digitalWrite()</i> <i>digitalRead()</i>
<i>if</i> <i>if...else</i> <i>for</i> <i>switch case</i> <i>while</i> <i>do... while</i>	Data Types	Analog I/O
	<i>void</i>	<i>analogReference()</i> <i>analogRead()</i>

break
continue
return
goto

Further Syntax

; (semicolon)
{ } (curly braces)
// (single line comment)
/ */* (multi-line comment)
#define
#include

Arithmetic Operators

= (assignment operator)
+ (addition)
- (subtraction)
*** (multiplication)
/ (division)
% (modulo)

Comparison Operators

== (equal to)
!= (not equal to)
< (less than)
> (greater than)
<= (less than or equal to)
>= (greater than or equal to)

Boolean Operators

&& (and)
|| (or)
! (not)

Pointer Access Operators

*** dereference operator
& reference operator

Bitwise Operators

boolean
char
unsigned char
byte
int
unsigned int
word
long
unsigned long
float
double
string - char array
String - object
array

Conversion

char()
byte()
int()
word()
long()
float()

Variable Scope & Qualifiers

variable scope
static
volatile
const

Utilities

sizeof()

analogWrite() - PWM

Advanced I/O

tone()
noTone()
shiftOut()
shiftIn()
pulseIn()

Time

millis()
micros()
delay()
delayMicroseconds()

Math

min()
max()
abs()
constrain()
map()
pow()
sqrt()

Trigonometry

sin()
cos()
tan()

Random Numbers

randomSeed()
random()

Bits and Bytes

lowByte()
highByte()
bitRead()
bitWrite()
bitSet()

& (bitwise and)
| (bitwise or)
^ (bitwise xor)
~ (bitwise not)
<< (bitshift left)
>> (bitshift right)

Compound Operators

++ (increment)
-- (decrement)
+= (compound addition)
-= (compound subtraction)
**=* (compound multiplication)
/= (compound division)
&= (compound bitwise and)
|= (compound bitwise or)

bitClear()
bit()

External Interrupts

attachInterrupt()
detachInterrupt()

Interrupts

interrupts()
noInterrupts()

Communication

Serial
Stream

- **setDataMode()** - Sets the SPI data mode: that is, clock polarity and phase. See the Wikipedia article on SPI for details.

SPI.setDataMode(mode)

- **transfer()** - Transfers one byte over the SPI bus, both sending and receiving.

SPI.transfer(val)

- **shiftOut()** - Shifts out a byte of data one bit at a time.

Note: if you're interfacing with a device that's clocked by rising edges, you'll need to make sure that the clock pin is low before the call to `shiftOut()`, e.g. with a call to `digitalWrite(clockPin, LOW)`.

shiftOut(dataPin, clockPin, bitOrder, value)

```
// Do this for MSBFIRST serial  
int data = 500;  
// shift out highbyte  
shiftOut(dataPin, clock, MSBFIRST, (data >> 8));  
// shift out lowbyte  
shiftOut(data, clock, MSBFIRST, data);
```

```
// Or do this for LSBFIRST serial
```

```

data = 500;
// shift out lowbyte
shiftOut(dataPin, clock, LSBFIRST, data);
// shift out highbyte
shiftOut(dataPin, clock, LSBFIRST, (data >> 8));

```

Example: For accompanying circuit, see the tutorial on controlling a 74HC595 shift register.

```

// Notes : Code for using a 74HC595 Shift Register to count from 0 to 255 //
//*****

```

```

//Pin connected to ST_CP of 74HC595
int latchPin = 8;
//Pin connected to SH_CP of 74HC595
int clockPin = 12;
////Pin connected to DS of 74HC595
int dataPin = 11;

```

```

void setup() {
  //set pins to output because they are addressed in the main loop
  pinMode(latchPin, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(clockPin, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(dataPin, OUTPUT);
}

```

```

void loop() {
  //count up routine
  for (int j = 0; j < 256; j++) {
    //ground latchPin and hold low for as long as you are transmitting
    digitalWrite(latchPin, LOW);
    shiftOut(dataPin, clockPin, LSBFIRST, j);
    //return the latch pin high to signal chip that it
    //no longer needs to listen for information
    digitalWrite(latchPin, HIGH);
    delay(1000);
  }
}

```

- **shiftIn()** - Shifts in a byte of data one bit at a time. Starts from either the most (i.e. the leftmost) or least (rightmost) significant bit. For each bit, the clock pin is pulled high, the next bit is read from the data line, and then the clock pin is taken low.

```

byte incoming = shiftIn(dataPin, clockPin, bitOrder)

```

- **LED: 13.** There is a built-in LED connected to digital pin 13. When the pin is HIGH value, the LED is on, when the pin is LOW, it's off.
- **TWI: 20 (SDA) and 21 (SCL).** Support TWI communication using the Wire library. Note that these pins are not in the same location as the TWI pins on the Duemilanove or Diecimila.

The Mega2560 has 16 analog inputs, each of which provide 10 bits of resolution (i.e. 1024 different values). By default they measure from ground to 5 volts, though is it possible to change the upper end of their range using the AREF pin and *analogReference()* function.

There are a couple of other pins on the board:

- **AREF.** Reference voltage for the analog inputs. Used with *analogReference()*.

>> **Warning:** *Don't use anything less than 0V or more than 5V for external reference voltage on the AREF pin! If you're using an external reference on the AREF pin, you must set the analog reference to EXTERNAL before calling analogRead(). Otherwise, you will short together the active reference voltage (internally grounded)*

- **Reset.** Bring this line LOW to reset the microcontroller. Typically used to add a reset button to shields which block the one on the board.

3.1.7.14-Communication: The Arduino Mega2560 has a number of facilities for communicating with a computer, another Arduino, or other microcontrollers. The ATmega2560 provides four hardware UARTs for TTL (5V) serial communication. AnATmega16U2 (ATmega 8U2 on the revision 1 and revision 2 boards) on the board channels one of these over USB and provides a virtual com port to software on the computer (Windows machines will need a .inf file, but OSX and Linux machines will recognize the board as a COM port automatically. The Arduino software includes a serial monitor which allows simple textual data to be sent to and from the board. The RX and TX LEDs on the board will flash when data is being transmitted via the ATmega8U2/ATmega16U2 chip and USB connection to the computer (but not for serial communication on pins 0 and 1).

A SoftwareSerial library allows for serial communication on any of the Mega2560's digital pins. The ATmega2560 also supports TWI and SPI communication. The Arduino software includes a Wire library to simplify use of the TWI bus; see the documentation for details. For SPI communication, use the SPI library.

Software Serial Library: The SoftwareSerial library has been developed to allow serial communication on other digital pins of the Arduino, using software to replicate the functionality (hence the name "SoftwareSerial"). It is possible to have multiple software serial ports with speeds up to 115200 bps. A parameter enables inverted signaling for devices which require that protocol.

Limitations: The library has the following known limitations:

- If using multiple software serial ports, only one can receive data at a time.

- Not all pins on the Mega and Mega 2560 support change interrupts, so only the following can be used for RX: 10, 11, 12, 13, 50, 51, 52, 53, 62, 63, 64, 65, 66, 67, 68, 69

Example

```
#include <SoftwareSerial.h>
```

```
SoftwareSerial mySerial(2, 3);
```

```
void setup()
```

```
{
  Serial.begin(57600);
  Serial.println("Goodnight moon!");
```

```
  // set the data rate for the SoftwareSerial port
  mySerial.begin(4800);
  mySerial.println("Hello, world?");
}
```

```
void loop() // run over and over
```

```
{
  if (mySerial.available())
    Serial.write(mySerial.read());
  if (Serial.available())
    mySerial.write(Serial.read());
}
```

❖ **Functions**

- *SoftwareSerial()*
- *available()*
- *begin()*
- *isListening()*
- *overflow()*
- *read()*
- *print()*
- *println()*
- *listen()*
- *write()*

Wire Library - This library allows you to communicate with I2C / TWI devices. On most Arduino boards, SDA (data line) is on analog input pin 4, and SCL (clock line) is on analog input pin 5. On the Arduino Mega, SDA is digital pin 20 and SCL is 21.

As of Arduino 1.0, the library inherits from the Stream functions, making it consistent with other read/write libraries. Because of this, send() and receive() have been replaced with read() and write().

❖ Functions

- *begin()*
- *begin(address)*
- *requestFrom(address, count)*
- *beginTransaction(address)*
- *endTransmission()*
- *write()*
- *byte available()*
- *byte read()*
- *onReceive(handler)*
- *onRequest(handler)*

3.1.7.15-Programming of ATmega 2560: The Arduino Mega can be programmed with the Arduino software (*here Arduino 1.0 is used*).

The ATmega2560 on the Arduino Mega comes preburned with a boot loader that allows you to upload new code to it without the use of an external hardware programmer. It communicates using the original STK500 protocol (reference, C header files).

We can also bypass the boot loader and program the microcontroller through the ICSP (In-Circuit Serial Programming) header; see these instructions for details.

3.1.7.16-Automatic (Software) Reset: Rather than requiring a physical press of the reset button before an upload, the Arduino Mega2560 is designed in a way that allows it to be reset by software running on a connected computer. One of the hardware flow control lines (DTR) of the ATmega8U2 is connected to the reset line of the ATmega2560 via a 100 nanofarad capacitor.

The Mega2560 contains a trace that can be cut to disable the auto-reset. The pads on either side of the trace can be soldered together to re-enable it. It's labeled "RESET-EN". You may also be able to disable the auto-reset by connecting a 110 ohm resistor from 5V to the reset line.

3.1.7.17-USB Overcurrent Protection: The Arduino Mega2560 has a resettable polyfuse that protects your computer's USB ports from shorts and overcurrent. Although most computers provide their own internal protection, the fuse provides an extra layer of protection. If more than 500 mA is applied to the USB port, the fuse will automatically break the connection until the short or overload is removed.

3.1.7.18-Shield Compatibility-The Mega2560 is designed to be compatible with most shields available. Digital pins 0 to 13 (and the adjacent AREF and GND pins), analog inputs 0 to 5, the power header, and ICSP header are all in equivalent locations. Further the main UART (serial port) is located on the same pins (0 and 1), as are external interrupts 0 and 1 (pins 2 and 3 respectively). SPI is available through the ICSP header on the Mega2560. Please note that I²C is not located on the same pins on the Mega (20 and 21) as the Duemilanove / Diecimila (analog inputs 4 and 5).

3.1.8-Bluetooth: Bluetooth is a proprietary open wireless technology standard for exchanging data over short distances (using short wavelength radio transmissions in the ISM band from 2400-2480 MHz) from fixed and mobile devices, creating personal area networks (PANs) with high levels of security. It can connect several devices, overcoming problems of synchronization.

Bluetooth is managed by the Bluetooth Special Interest Group, which has more than 15,000 member companies in the areas of telecommunication, computing, networking, and consumer electronics.

A master Bluetooth device can communicate with a maximum of seven devices in a piconet (an ad-hoc computer network using Bluetooth technology), though not all devices support this limit. The devices can switch roles, by agreement, and the slave can become the master.

The Bluetooth Core Specification provides for the connection of two or more piconets to form a scatternet, in which certain devices simultaneously play the master role in one piconet and the slave role in another.

Bluetooth is a standard wire-replacement communications protocol primarily designed for low power consumption, with a short range (power-class-dependent, but effective ranges vary in practice).

Class	Maximum permitted power		Range (m)
	(mW)	(dBm)	
Class 1	100	20	~100
Class 2	2.5	4	~10
Class 3	1	0	~5

Version	Data rate	Maximum application throughput
Version 1.2	1 Mbit/s	0.7 Mbit/s
Version 2.0 + EDR	3 Mbit/s	2.1 Mbit/s
Version 3.0 + HS	See Version 3.0+HS.	
Version 4.0	See Version 4.0LE.	

3.1.8.1-Wireless communication with PC and Arduino board using Bluetooth:

Equipment used are a *Bluetooth Dongle (Enter -v2.0 used for laptop)* and *Bluetooth Module (BlueSmirf Bluetooth Modules used with Arduino Mega board)*

3.2- Software: The software used in this work are Arduino 1.0, Simple-serial-arduino-scope, MS-Excel, Processing 1.5.1, LabVIEW-2010, LIFA, Multisim 11.0, Wiring 0100, etc.

3.2.1- Arduino 1.0- The open-source Arduino environment makes it easy to write code and upload it to the i/o board. It runs on Windows, Mac OS X, and Linux. The environment is written in Java and based on Processing, avr-gcc, and other open source software.

The Arduino development environment contains a text editor for writing code, a message area, a text console, a toolbar with buttons for common functions, and a series of menus. It connects to the Arduino hardware to upload programs and communicate with them.

Software written using Arduino are called *sketches*. These sketches are written in the text editor. Sketches are saved with the file extension *.ino*. It has features for cutting/pasting and for searching/replacing text. The message area gives feedback while saving and exporting and also displays errors. The console displays text output by the Arduino environment including complete error messages and other information. It is a very rich software have many and many facilities to make it user friendly. It's some main facilities are:

Verify, Upload, New, Open, Save, Cut, Copy, Paste, Serial Monitor, Board selector, port selector, sketchbook etc.

3.2.1.1- Serial Monitor: It displays serial data being sent from the Arduino board (USB or serial board).its opener is located at the right-above corner of window. To send data to the board, enter text and click on the "send" button or press enter. Choose the baud rate from the drop-down that matches the rate passed to Serial. begin in your sketch. Note that on Mac or Linux, the Arduino board will reset (rerun your sketch from the beginning) when you connect with the serial monitor to see the output data in real time.

3.2.2-Microsoft Excel- To see the data of serial monitor in graphical form we can use the simple and very familiar software MS-Excel which is easily available in most of the systems.

3.2.3-Wiring0100- Wiring is an open-source programming framework for microcontrollers. Since it an open- source programming framework, so it can also be used to program arduino mega board. Wiring is an open project initiated by Hernando Barragán. Wiring started at the Interaction Design Institute Ivrea in Italy and it is currently developed at the Universidad de Los Andes, Architecture and Design School in Colombia. .

For some program I have also used here.

Wiring allows writing cross-platform software to control devices attached to a wide range of microcontroller boards to create all kinds of creative coding, interactive objects, spaces or physical experiences.

- ❖ Roadmap include support for multiple hardware architectures "Cores"
 - The current AVR8 Core supports the *Wiring hardware* and *any hardware* based on the AVR atmega processors. AVR Xmega, AVR Tiny, TI MSP430, Microchip PIC24/32 Series and STM M3 ARM Cores will be available soon.
 - Simple third party atmel hardware support integration
 - For GNU/Linux, Mac OS X, and Windows
 - Over 100 libraries extend the software
 - Interactive programs using 2D, 3D or PDF output
 - OpenGL integration for accelerated 3D
 - For GNU/Linux, Mac OS X, and Windows
 - Projects run online or as double-clickable applications

- Over 100 libraries extend the software into sound, video, computer vision, and more...

3.2.4- Processing-1.5.1- Processing is an open source programming language and environment for people who want to create images, animations, and interactions.

Initially developed to serve as a software sketchbook and to teach fundamentals of computer programming within a visual context, Processing also has evolved into a tool for generating finished professional work. Today, there are tens of thousands of students, artists, designers, researchers, and hobbyists who use Processing for learning, prototyping, and production.

Using Processing interface with Arduino it can be possible to see real time graphical view of serial data of Arduino serial monitor. But because of some driver or operating system problem I could not try it. Yet processing playground is helpful in the study of Arduino programming because it is the base of Arduino programming development.

3.2.5-Multisim-11.0: NI Multisim (formerly MultiSIM) is an electronic schematic capture and simulation program which is part of a suite of circuit design programs, along with NI Ultiboard. Multisim is one of the few circuit design programs to employ the original Berkeley SPICE based software simulation. Multisim was originally created by a company named Electronics Workbench, which is now a division of National Instruments. Multisim includes microcontroller simulation (formerly known as MultiMCU), as well as integrated import and export features to the Printed Circuit Board layout software in the suite, NI Ultiboard.

3.2.6-LabVIEW-2010: LabVIEW (Laboratory Virtual Instrumentation Engineering Workbench) is a system design platform and development environment for a visual programming language from National Instruments.

The graphical language is named "G" (not to be confused with G-code). Originally released for the Apple Macintosh in 1986, LabVIEW is commonly used for data acquisition, instrument control, and industrial automation on a variety of platforms including Microsoft Windows, various versions of UNIX, Linux, and Mac OS X.

In LabVIEW execution of program is determined by the structure of a graphical block diagram (the LV source code) on which the programmer connects different function-nodes by drawing wires.

3.2.6.1-NI LabVIEW Interface for Arduino Toolkit (LIFA)- The NI LabVIEW Interface for Arduino Toolkit helps you easily interface with the Arduino microcontroller using LabVIEW.

With this toolkit and LabVIEW, you can control or acquire data from the Arduino microcontroller. Once the information is in LabVIEW, analyze it using the hundreds of built-in LabVIEW libraries, develop algorithms to control the Arduino hardware, and present your findings on a polished user interface.

A sketch for the Arduino microcontroller acts as an I/O engine that interfaces with LabVIEW VIs through a serial connection. This helps you quickly move information from Arduino pins to LabVIEW without adjusting the communication, synchronization, or even a single line of C code. Using the common Open, Read/Write, Close convention in LabVIEW, you can access the digital, analog, pulse-width-modulated, I2C, and SPI signals of the Arduino microcontroller. To learn how the under-the-hood functionality works so you can modify or extend it, look inside the subVIs or open the Arduino sketch.

Note: The Arduino microcontroller must be connected to the computer with LabVIEW through a USB, serial, Bluetooth, or XBee link. This toolkit does not provide for headless operation.

Advantages to use LIFA with Arduino:

- Easy access to Arduino DIO, AI, PWM, I2C, and SPI from LabVIEW
- I/O engine sketch to load on Arduino
- Examples for basic tasks and sensors
- Wireless with Bluetooth or XBee
- Loop rates: USB tethered (200 Hz) and wireless (25 Hz)
- Open Arduino sketch and toolkit VIs help you customize functionality

Chapter-4

Methodology and circuit design

4.1-Body Temperature sensing:

Description: The TMP36 is a low voltage, precision centigrade temperature sensor. It provides a voltage output that is linearly proportional to the Celsius temperature. It also doesn't require any external calibration to provide typical accuracies of $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ at $+25^\circ\text{C}$ and $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ over the -40°C to $+125^\circ\text{C}$ temperature range. We like it because it's so easy to use: Just give the device a ground and 2.7 to 5.5 VDC and read the voltage on the Vout pin. The output voltage can be converted to temperature easily using the scale factor of $10\text{ mV}/^\circ\text{C}$:

Features:

- Voltage Input: 2.7 V to 5.5 VDC
- $10\text{ mV}/^\circ\text{C}$ scale factor
- $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ accuracy over temperature
- $\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ linearity
- Operating Range: -40°C to $+125^\circ\text{C}$
- Size: TO-92 package (about $0.2'' \times 0.2'' \times 0.2''$) with three leads
- Temperature range: -40°C to 150°C / -40°F to 302°F
- Output range: 0.1V (-40°C) to 2.0V (150°C) but accuracy decreases after 125°C
- Power supply: 2.7V to 5.5V only, 0.05 mA current draw

How to measure temperature!

Output voltage vs Temperature

To convert the voltage to temperature, simply use the basic formula:

$$\text{Temp in } ^\circ\text{C} = [(\text{Vout in mV}) - 500] / 10$$

So for example, if the voltage out is 1V that means that the temperature is:

$$((1000\text{ mV} - 500) / 10) = 50^\circ\text{C}$$

Testing the temperature sensor:

How to connect this on board:

Using a 5V Arduino, and connecting the sensor directly into an Analog pin, you can use these formulas to turn the 10-bit analog reading into a temperature:

Voltage at pin in milliVolts = (reading from ADC) * (5000/1024)

This formula converts the number 0-1023 from the ADC into 0-5000mV (= 5V)

If I use a 3.3V Arduino, you'll want to use this:

Voltage at pin in milliVolts = (reading from ADC) * (3300/1024)

This formula converts the number 0-1023 from the ADC into 0-3300mV (= 3.3V)

Then, to convert millivolts into temperature, use this formula:

Centigrade temperature = [(analog voltage in mV) - 500] / 10

This formula converts millivolts value in °C.

Fahrenheit temperature = (temperature °C * 9.0 / 5.0) + 32.0

This formula converts °C value in °F.

Now we open the **Arduino 1.0** playground and then write the program in processing language.

Then we upload this on Mega 2560 board. Firstly it reads the surrounding temp. and then after contacting this with body it reads the body temp.

We can set its sampling rate in programming as:

```
delay 1000; //waiting 1 second for next sample ie. 1 samp/ second
```

```
delay 100; // waiting 1/10 second for next sample ie. 10 samp/ second
```

Then after we open its serial monitor to see the output data serially, this shows the variance of temperature of body in °C and °F with its corresponding voltage value. By selecting only °F output data while we can show only °F value serially on serial monitor. As:

```
// now print out the temperature
```

```
float temperatureC = (voltage - 0.5) * 100 ; //converting from 10 mv per degree wit 500 mV offset
```

```
//to degrees ((voltage - 500mV) times 100)
```

```
// now convert to Fahrenheit
```

```
float temperatureF = (temperatureC * 9.0 / 5.0) + 32.0;
```

```
Serial.print(temperatureF); Serial.println(""); // print only numerical values of °F temp.
```


Writing sketch and compilation

Running with serial monitor

Now I took a segment of data and show this easily in waveform for GUI (Graphical User Interface).

Sketching window with serial monitor and GUI during temperature acquisition

4.1.1 Wireless transmission of temperature data:

Equipment: Equipment used are a Bluetooth Dongle (*Enter -v2.0 used for laptop*) and Bluetooth (*BlueSmirf*) Modules used with Arduino Mega board).

Process: Connect your Bluesmirf module to the Ground/Power/Rx/Tx pins of Arduino microcontroller. Connect the Arduino to AC power or battery power.

- Note that the Rx pin of Bluetooth module with Tx of Arduino board and vice versa.
- Plug in USB Bluetooth adaptor into your computer or laptop (I used enter v2)
- Install the Bluetooth Software . Reboot after install.
- Open up newly installed Bluetooth Settings. Click 'New Connection'. Select 'Custom Mode Setup' and click next. It will search for devices, and it should detect Bluetooth Radios (which is the BlueSmirf), select this then click next. I did not need to enter a passkey, but if it asks you, the passkey for BlueSmirf is 'default'. It will then register a COM port. NOW, uncheck the tick box at the bottom, and then next to the drop down menu displaying the COM ports, uncheck the box which says 'auto connect'. Then click next. The BlueSmirf is now added.
- Now it should appear in your Bluetooth Settings window. Right click on it and click connect - nothing will happen to the BlueSmirf but the computer will establish a link. If you highlight it and click the 'detail' button, it will remind you which COM port its using under the settings.
- Now open up Arduino platform to talk to BlueSmirf/Arduino wirelessly.
- The line `println(Serial.list());` will print all the COM ports on your computer. You will need to change the line `port1 = new Serial(this, Serial.list()[9], 9600);` where [9] represents the COM port in the list that corresponds to your BlueSmirfs COM port. You can alternatively use something like this: `port1 = new Serial(this, "COM4")`.
- Then run the Arduino program, and a LED should now light up on the BlueSmirf - you are now connected! And if you have programmed the Arduino right, when you click the buttons to send data, the LED should turn on and off.

4.2- GSR (Galvanic Skin Response) or SCR (Skin Conductivity Response) acquisition:

- **Instruments required:** In-amp MCP6002, thin copper strip, Velcro strip Resistors R1=100k, R2=220Ω, R3=10k, R4=1M, R5=3.3M, R6=1k; Capacitors C1=10nF, C2=0.1μF, C3=0.1μF, Diode IN4007, LED

Circuit diagram for GSR component arranged on bread board GSR signal acquisition

Process:

- Firstly we solder the two copper strips with multi-core copper wires smoothly.
- Then attach these strips with Velcro strips to make fine wearable it in fingers.
- Arrange the component as shown in above figures on bread board or PCB as dense as possible.
- Take the output between the LED and R2 for arduino and then program it by PC via Bluetooth like temperature sensing.

Here high precision op-amp is use for low cast. Since here GSR signal is of mili-volt range so op-amp perform its amplification but for more accurate amplification we use here in-amp like INA114.

sketching window with serial monitor and GUI during GSR acquisition

4.3-EMG (Electromyogram) acquisition:

- **Instruments required:** EMG Electrodes (3), In-amp-INA128, Dual supply battery (+9V and -9V), resistor R1=120 Ω, capacitors C1=100μF, C2=100μF.

Process:

- Firstly implant two EMG electrodes (mutual difference of 1 inch = 2.51 cm) and the next one reference one on knee.
- Then arrange the component as shown in above figures on bread board or PCB as dense as possible.

Connect the output of this EMG sensor at analog input of Arduino which is already connected with Bluetooth and then program for this on PC like temperature sensor.

Sketching window with serial monitor and GUI during EMG acquisition

4.4- Heart Rate / Pulse Rate acquisition:

- **Instruments required:** Infrared LED, Photo detector, Resistors R1=100 M, R2=100Ω, R3=100Ω, Capacitor C1=4.7μF, In-amp SA5230/ INA114.

Circuit diagram for HR/PR

component arranged on bread board

Process:

- Firstly arrange the component as shown in above figures on bread board or PCB as dense as possible.
- Connect the output of circuit (here the green wire) to one of the analog input of arduino.
- Then program arduino (connected with Bluetooth) for pulse sensor.

➤ Then finally we can get data on my PC via Bluetooth .

Heart rate acquisition circuit designed in Multisim 11.0

Sketching window with serial monitor and GUI during EMG acquisition

4.5-ECG acquisition:

- **Instruments required:** ECG electrodes (3), In-amp AD624AD, resistors 47k (3), 680k (1), 10k(1), 4.7k(1), capacitor 0.1μF(3), 1.0μF(2), potentiometer 10k(1).

Circuit for ECG sensing

illustration of electrode placement

ECG acquisition circuit designed in Multisim 11.0

Process:

- Design circuit on PCB as possible as dense.

- Connect electrodes on chest and leg as shown in fig. and connect output at Arduino analog input (connected with Bluetooth module).
- Program to Arduino and get data wirelessly.

4.6-EEG acquisition:

EEG acquisition could not done because of more noisy response. But it can be done for bipolar single channel using two electrodes on two corresponding position of head and the third at below the ear position and then filtering and processing.

4.7-Blood Pressure acquisition:

- **Instruments required:** Blood pressure sensor, resister 1k.

Programming for blood pressure acquisition:

```
blood_pressure | Arduino 1.0
File Edit Sketch Tools Help
blood_pressure
/* FSR testing sketch.

Connect one end of FSR to power, the other end to Analog 0.
Then connect one end of a 10K resistor from Analog 0 to ground

For more information see www.ladyada.net/learn/sensors/fsr.html */

int fsrPin = 0; // the FSR and 10K pullup are connected to A0
unsigned long fsrReading; // the analog reading from the FSR resistor divider
unsigned long fsrVoltage; // the analog reading converted to voltage
unsigned long fsrResistance; // The voltage converted to resistance, can be very big so make "long"
unsigned long fsrConductance;
unsigned long fsrForce; // Finally, the resistance converted to force

void setup(void) {
  Serial.begin(9600); // We'll send debugging information via the Serial monitor
}

void loop(void) {
  fsrReading = analogRead(fsrPin);
  Serial.print("Analog reading fsrReading = ");
  Serial.println(fsrReading);

  // analog voltage reading ranges from about 0 to 1023 which maps to 0V to 5V (= 5000uV)
  fsrVoltage = map(fsrReading, 0, 1023, 0, 5000);
  Serial.print("Voltage reading in uV fsrVoltage = ");
  Serial.println(fsrVoltage);

  // ...
}

Compiling sketch...
60
Arduino Mega 2560 or Mega ADK on COM33
Computer 4:57 PM 14-Feb-12
```

5.1- Motor controlled by human body temperature or other bio-signal:

We've seen some motion controlling by some bio-signals such in case of voice recognition system and others.

Here in this task I wrote a program in processing language and run it on arduino 1.0 to detect the required or specified level to make high voltage (5 volt) at specified SPI pins.

```
kanav | Arduino 1.0
File Edit Sketch Tools Help
kanav
int sensorPin = 0; //the analog pin the TMP36's Vout (sense) pin is connected to
//the resolution is 10 mV / degree centigrade with a
//500 mV offset to allow for negative temperatures

int led = 9;

void setup()
{
  Serial.begin(9600); //Start the serial connection with the computer
  //to view the result open the serial monitor
}

pinMode(9, OUTPUT);
}

void loop()
{
  // run over and over again
  //getting the voltage reading from the temperature sensor
  int reading = analogRead(sensorPin);

  // converting that reading to voltage, for 5.0v arduino use 5.0
  float voltage = reading * 5.0;
  voltage /= 1024.0;

  // now print out the temperature
  float temperatureC = (voltage - 0.5) * 100; //converting from 10 mV per degree with 500 mV offset
  //to degrees ((voltage - 500mV) times 100)

  // now convert to Fahrenheit
  float temperatureF = (temperatureC * 9.0 / 5.0) + 32.0;
}
```

Program for motor driving by body temperature variance

I connected a small motor at this specified pin. On detecting the high and low level of temperature it got run or stop.

Logic for running motor between 90°F and 100°F

```
//if (Serial.available())    // If data is available,
//{
// val = Serial.read();    // read it and store it in val
// if (90.0 < temperatureF < 100.0)    // If 'High' was received,
// {
//   digitalWrite(10 , HIGH); // turn the led on
// }
// else if (temperatureF < 90.0)    // If 'Low was received
// {
//   digitalWrite(10 , LOW);; // turn led off
// }
//}
```

Chapter 6

Wireless Sensor Networking over Wireless Body Area Networking

6.1- Concept: The development of WBAN technology considers wireless personal area network (WPAN) technologies for communications on, near and around the human body. A WBAN system can use WPAN wireless technologies as gateways to reach longer ranges.

In this networking system firstly the data collected from different sensors are transmitted by arduino to host station (gateway) via Bluetooth or zigbee. The *gateway* is the data collector center as near as possible between a specified group of soldier. If this station is of low range, it should be movable with the group members. It should be of multi-channel capability and long range transmission capacity.

The gateway transmits data collected from different nodes to base station for analysis and medical monitoring.

- Temperature sensing and monitoring on PC via Bluetooth is successfully done.
- Galvanic skin response sensing and monitoring on PC via Bluetooth is done successfully.
- Heart rate sensing and monitoring on PC via Bluetooth is done successfully.
- EMG sensing and monitoring on PC via Bluetooth is done but with some noise.
- Blood pressure sensing program is ready but because of unavailability of BP sensor it could not be done fully.
- ECG sensing is not done completely due to noise but its programming and circuit designing in Multisim 11.0 is done.
- EEG sensing is a multichannel more sensitive to noise and more time taken task so it could not be done with these.
- Because of some sewing problem the sensors could not be sewed into a wearable cloth but a sewing expert can attach these sensors where I have located for these.

Here wireless data transmission from single node to PC is done but because of single availability multi-node network could not be completed. But it could be done for multi-node network also.

APPENDIX

References:

- <http://arduino.cc/>
- www.bhtmem.fi/book/
- <http://arduino.cc/forum/index.php?action=pm;sa=send>